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Technical Report: Designing and Implementation of Harmonised Protocols for the Detection and Typing of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. in the European Union

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project, *Integrative Action-2.2*, OH-Harmony-Cap: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants.

<https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>

OH-Harmony-Cap is a 3-year project, which aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, adaptabilities and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level. The quantitative description of current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols will identify and possibly close the gaps and support future studies of how best to detect and characterise foodborne pathogens across the One Health sectors. The OH-Harmony-Cap Consortium comprises 18 One Health EJP partners.

1. Introduction

The application of harmonised and appropriate procedures for sampling, detection, characterisation, data management and reporting procedures in the human and food/veterinary fields and in laboratories testing food, feed and environmental samples across the European Union (EU) would greatly assist in the effectiveness of public health surveillance systems and would allow better risk assessment through improved result comparisons. This is essential in outbreak detection and investigation but also in the ongoing monitoring of foodborne and zoonotic pathogens. Despite improvements in recent years, differences in capability, capacity and communication practices have hampered the development of an integrative system. Moreover, the possibility to share harmonised data, such as from strain characterisation, is pivotal in a public health effective risk assessment perspective.

The main objectives of the EJP Joint Integrative Project OH Harmony-Cap are:

- [1] to collect information on current abilities, adaptabilities, capacities and interoperability both at the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level, focusing on a set of microbial foodborne hazards;
- [2] to provide a quantitative description of the current and best practices;
- [3] to contribute to the development of harmonised protocols and
- [4] to identify potential research fields to detect and characterise foodborne pathogens across the one health sectors. The target organisms considered in the project are Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* spp. and the determination of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp..

This document represents the final report of the Work Package 4 (WP4) of the OH-Harmony-Cap Project, which aims at the definition of harmonised procedures for the detection and typing of the above mentioned model organisms. A general description of the methods for achieving this goal will be presented, and the activities carried out in WP4 and the outputs (consisting in the proposed harmonised procedure, ranking of methods or decision tree) will be described in different sections, corresponding each one to:

- Pathogenic *E. coli* (STEC and ETEC)
- *Cryptosporidium* spp.
- AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp.

The model organisms have been selected for the following reasons:

- STEC are foodborne pathogens of public health concern, able to induce severe disease in humans, such as haemorrhagic colitis and the haemolytic uremic syndrome, and the infection may be fatal in a number of cases,
- ETEC strains have frequently been associated to the so-called travellers' diarrhoea, but represent an emerging public health concern, also in high-income countries. In the pig

production, ETEC is one of the main causes of post weaning diarrhoea in piglets resulting in the premature death of a large number of piglets each day,

- *Cryptosporidium* spp. are important waterborne pathogens worldwide and a leading cause of mortality from waterborne gastrointestinal diseases. Moreover, it is an important pathogen for livestock,
- AMR is considered an emerging problem in the different sectors of the One Health system.

We acknowledge that much work has been done at the international level, by European Union Reference Laboratories (EURLs) and the European agencies European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). In this project, we saw an opportunity to work on the harmonisation of the procedures based on the protocols already in use at reference laboratories, to propose fit-for-purpose methods that may be made available and exploited in the different sectors. In particular, the protocols for characterisation may be adopted and harmonised across sectors, providing an alignment in the methodologies applied.

The resulting proposed procedures have been selected based on protocols collected at international level, shared by European public health, veterinary and food testing institutions and National Reference Laboratories (NRLs) reached via the EURLs for the relevant microorganisms, as described later on.

2. Collection of protocols (WP4 Task 1 –M25-M32) Task leader ISS (Rosangela Tozzoli), Deputy ANSES (Melanie Gay)

Laboratory procedures and protocols for the selected microorganisms, STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium* spp. and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp., have been collected from OH-Harmony-Cap partners and by sending the request to the networks of reference laboratories operating in the areas of public health and veterinary/food safety.

In particular, besides reaching out to the projects' participants, a request for sharing the protocols was sent to the Head of ECDC Food and Waterborne Diseases (FWD) programme and to the Directors of the relevant EURLs: EURL for *E. coli*, EURL for Parasites and EURL for Antimicrobial Resistance, who forwarded the request to the respective networks. This approach aimed to collect the protocols used by NRLs operating in the different sectors, in order to have the possibility to compare and evaluate high-level procedures, and to select the proposed harmonised procedures from the methodologies in use in International networks of laboratories.

Overall 23 institutions operating in the public health, veterinary health and/or food safety /fields, including the relevant EURLs, either participants of the OH-Harmony-Cap project or from other networks, responded to our request. As for the OH-Harmony-Cap participating institutes, most of them were also part of the networks of laboratories we reached out to, and the protocols were shared by:

- French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, ANSES (Food/Veterinary sector)

- Animal and Plant Health Agency, APHA, UK (Veterinary sector)
- Federal Institute for Risk Assessment, BfR, Germany (Food/Veterinary sector)
- Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária, INIAV, Portugal (Food/Veterinary sector)
- Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge, INSA, Portugal (Public Health)
- Italian National Institute of Health, ISS (Public Health, hosting the EURLs for *E. coli* and for Parasites)
- The Public Health Agency of Sweden, FOHM (Public Health)
- National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, RIVM, The Netherlands (Public Health)
- Swedish Food Agency, SLV, Sweden (Food Sector)
- Statens Serum Institut, Denmark (Public Health)
- National Veterinary Institute, SVA, Sweden (Food/Veterinary sector)
- Norwegian Veterinary Institute, NVI, Norway (Veterinary sector)

In addition, six laboratories working in public health sector and six operating in the food and veterinary sector replied to our request through the Networks of EURLs and ECDC FWD or *via* direct contact.

Different kinds of documents were shared and collected, including Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), book chapters, PhD thesis, papers, EFSA and ECDC documents, documents retrieved from EURL AMR website, national standards for microbiology investigation or information about the procedures in use.

The protocols/documents shared and considered in the following WP4 tasks consisted in:

- ✓ 49 protocols on STEC
- ✓ 6 protocols on ETEC
- ✓ 7 documents on both ETEC/STEC
- ✓ 20 protocols on *Cryptosporidium* spp.
- ✓ 17 protocols on AMR in *Salmonella* and/or *Campylobacter*
- ✓ 2 documents providing information on the detection and typing of STEC, *Cryptosporidium* spp., AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*
- ✓ 1 document on *Cryptosporidium* spp., AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

Additionally, some institutes also reported that ISO standards and EURL methods were in use.

3. Evaluation of the protocols collected (WP4 Task 2-M31-39) Task leader SVA (Karin Troell), Deputy ANSES (Melanie Gay)

A primary evaluation of the collection of procedures applied by laboratories involved in the detection and characterisation of the model organisms was conducted. In particular, the aim of this task consisted in a preliminary assessment of the procedures and the production of summaries in table format in order to ease the comparison of the protocols. This made it possible to identify similarities among the protocols applied and for ranking and selection of harmonised procedures in WP4-T3.

This activity was divided in three different subtasks:

WP4-T2-S1: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of STEC/ETEC

WP4-T2-S2: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

WP4-T2-S3: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium* spp.

Three groups were formed consisting each of four to six WP4 participants, experts in the microorganisms considered in each sub-task. The constitution of the expert groups were also balanced among public health and food/veterinary sectors, institutes and expertise of the participants.

The first step of this activity was to agree on a scheme for summarizing the protocols, a table including the details considered as priority from the experts to illustrate the methods. It was addressed in each group of experts, to adapt the summary table to each model organism. In particular, information such as the methodologies utilised in the protocols, the type of samples, the targets of the procedures, as well as specific comments have been included in the evaluation tables.

Many of the protocols received were in native language of the providers. In this respect, the opportunity to request support for professional translation was evaluated, but based on the different nationalities and language skills of the experts enrolled in this task, it was not needed.

The protocols evaluated in each subtask and included in the output tables produced were as follows:

WP4-T2-S1: 53 protocols for STEC/ETEC

WP4-T2-S2: 10 protocols for *Campylobacter* AMR and 9 protocols for *Salmonella* AMR

WP4-T2-S3: 18 protocols for *Cryptosporidium* spp.

The work was distributed among the participants enrolled, and the evaluation tables produced.

The output tables produced per subtask is attached as Annexes 1-3, with anonymized institute names.

WP4-T2-S1: Evaluation of protocols for STEC/ETEC

The protocols collected were based on different methodologies, including microbiological, cellular biology, serological and molecular biology techniques. The sample types included environmental samples, biological material from animals, such as faeces and swabs, foodstuffs, specimen from humans, comprising faeces, urines, blood and tissue samples, as well as mixed cultures and isolated strains. An evaluation table was proposed by the subtask leader and agreed among the group of experts. The characteristics reported in the evaluation table aimed mainly to describe the principle and the targets of each method, together with a summary of the protocol itself. The experts also included a comment on the adaptability of the protocol in different laboratories (e.g. if the instrument was easily available or if the technique was used in diagnostic laboratories). Several protocols described the detection of targets by conventional PCR or real time PCR amplification, with good candidates for the proposed harmonised procedures commonly used in most of the diagnostic laboratories. Two protocols for the characterization of STEC were based on the application of whole genome sequencing (WGS).

WP4-T2-S2: Evaluation of protocols for *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* AMR

Protocols were collected from both public health and veterinary institutes. The main method used among the laboratories, from which protocols were collected, was broth microdilution. A few laboratories used disk diffusion. A majority stated that the methods they use were according to 2013/652/EU (from 2021 replaced by 2020/1729/EU) which describes the harmonised monitoring of AMR of zoonoses and zoonotic agents. Evaluation tables were proposed by the sub-task leader and agreed among the group of experts enrolled.

WP4-T2-S3: Evaluation of protocols for *Cryptosporidium* spp.

Protocols collected for *Cryptosporidium* spp. represented methods for either purification/enrichment, detection (microscopy or molecular) or molecular typing. The protocols were also developed for different matrices, such as faeces and water. The *Cryptosporidium* team adapted the evaluation table to have three subtables “purification/enrichment”, “detection” and “typing”. The evaluation table completed for each protocol and aimed to describe the principle of the method, the sample material and the targets, and a brief summary of the protocol. The experts of the team also included comments on the adaptability of the protocol in different laboratories, if the method could be used for quantification, and if there were alternative targets.

Groups of experts:

WP4-T2-S1 leader Robert Soderlund (SVA), team: Rosangela Tozzoli (ISS), Flemming Scheutz (SSI), Angela van Hoek (RIVM), Angela Pista (INSA), Nadia Boisen (SSI)

WP4-T2-S2 leader Marit Pringle (SVA), team: Karl Pedersen (SVA), Jeppe Boel (SSI), Isabelle Kempf (ANSES), Jannice Schau Sletteemås (NVI)

WP4-T2-S3 leader Karin Troell (SVA), team: Jessica Beser (FOHM), Pikka Jokelainen (SSI), Rune Stensvold (SSI), Melanie Gay (ANSES), Jacinto Gomes (INIAV), Mirosław Rozycki (PIWET), Ioana Bujila (FOHM)

4. Ranking and selection of the procedures (WP4 Task 3-M39-M50) Task leader PIWET (Mirosław Rozycki), Deputy ANSES (Melanie Gay)

The aim of this activity was to define harmonised procedures to be proposed and applied in the training sessions organized in WP5 of the OH-Harmony-Cap project. Moreover, this output will be disseminated to the networks operating in different sectors. To achieve the objective of selecting the procedures for the detection and typing of the model organisms, a ranking approach was first applied. However, depending on the target, different strategies have been used, either to assign scores to the collected protocols or to compare them.

As in the former task, WP4 participants, from different sectors, were enrolled in small groups to work on each model organisms:

WP4-T3-S1: Ranking of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of STEC/ETEC

WP4-T3-S2: Ranking of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

WP4-T3-S3: Ranking of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium* spp.

A preliminary discussion among WP4 participants, with the support of the task leaders, led to the decision of using ranking tables, based on specific characteristics of the methods. This approach was fine-tuned and adapted to each model organism, in order to carry out the ranking of the protocols collected. These features were assigned scores 3, 2 and 1, with 3 being the best scenario. The 0 score assign in cases where information was lacking. Hereafter the approaches applied in the different subtasks are reported, whereas the proposed harmonised procedures are annexed to this report.

WP4-T3-S1: Ranking of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of STEC/ETEC

The work of the group was carried out either through webcalls or in the framework of the project meeting 9-11 November 2021, Dublin, Ireland. The ranking table was adjusted by the group, in order to meet the requirements needed for this specific group of pathogens. Once defined, the ranking tables were pre-tested in an exercise by the experts on a set of the same protocols to fine-tune both the tables and the ranking ability. Following this exercise the adjustments needed were implemented and the ranking tables were finalized.

Several features were taken into account for the ranking and these are reported in the STEC and ETEC ranking table annexed to this report, where the laboratories' names have been anonymized.

In particular, these were included:

- performance parameters
- accreditation of the method
- if the method concerned only screening or if it also described isolation in case of the detection methods
- if the method was an international standard, an EURL method, a national standard or a published method
- the ease of implementation
- the equipment and facilities needed
- the complexity of samples' preparation
- if the results could be compared among OH sectors
- the cost and duration of analysis, including the man-hours
- if commercial kits were applied
- the possibility of high throughput
- easiness of results' interpretation.

Besides the above-mentioned features, the group identified essential criteria for either STEC and ETEC detection or typing. The criteria defined were as follows:

- ✓ STEC detection

Detection of all STEC types: 3 points yes all types, 2 points all but one or a few STEC types, and 1 point when only a subset was detected

- ✓ ETEC detection

Detection of ETEC strains producing either heat stable (ST) and heat labile toxins (LT): 3 points if both genes detected, 1 point in case only LT or ST was detected

- ✓ STEC characterization

Detection/characterization of all STEC types, namely *stx* genes subtyping and detection of *eae* and *aggR* genes (a score of 3 for the protocols describing *stx* subtyping or *eae* or *aggR*, and 1 if none of them).

The latter criterion is in line with the recent International scientific discussion, which identifies the determination of the *stx* subtyping and the presence of *eae* and enteroaggregative *E. coli* colonization factors as the most efficient approach for STEC risk assessment (2-3).

- ✓ ETEC characterization

Detection of both ST and LT and ETEC colonization factors (CF) (a score of 3 for toxins and CF, 1 only toxins detected).

Besides these features and criteria, the possibility that the methods could be tested in external quality assessments and the description of reference materials in the protocols was reported as an additional information, even if not scored.

The experts participating in this task operated either in public health or food/veterinary sectors, and received a set of original protocols collected together with the evaluation tables produced in task 2, to aid the ranking. The participants did not receive protocols from their own laboratory, but were requested to score procedures from other institutes. Each participant applied the ranking on five to six protocols. Some of the information needed for the ranking was missing, namely the performance characteristics of the procedures and if they were accredited. As for the sensitivity and specificity, it could be in some cases retrieved from the literature, but this did not apply for all methods. The missing information, particularly concerning the accreditation, were collected for all the methods by direct contact via email with the protocol providers.

In general, procedures commonly applied in diagnostic laboratories, such as PCR, were assigned high ranks in the respective features, as well as those including easy sample preparation, and easiness in DNA preparation and results interpretation.

This exercise resulted in some high score methods, from which it was decided to select the proposed harmonised procedures. Following the ranking of the protocols by the experts, a virtual meeting to discuss the outcome was organized, and the following conclusions can be drawn:

- ✓ During the ranking, conventional PCR has been scored higher than Real Time PCR for several reasons: i) it is the most widely applied, and ii) it has the lower cost.
- ✓ As expected, the laboratories operating in the Food/veterinary sector are applying the standard method ISO TS 13136:2012 for the detection of STEC and this represents an inescapable requirement for the official laboratories, making it impossible to propose a single procedure to be applied in all sectors. The ISO TS 13136:2012 procedure was also evaluated during the

exercise, and it indeed ranked high, after one protocol for the detection of STEC in human samples.

- ✓ For the sake of harmonisation, even though it is not possible to propose a single procedure to be applied in all sectors, the same approach may be applied. The ISO TS 13136:2012 targets STEC based on the detection of presence of *Stx*-coding genes, and a similar approach should be applied for the proposed method for detection of STEC in public health laboratories, rather than targeting STEC subgroups (e.g. serogroups). This was the rationale behind one of the criteria for the group of experts.
- ✓ For the detection of STEC, the highest-ranking protocol was based on conventional PCR. This protocol is applied to different specimens, including faecal samples, bacterial cultures, pure cultures, swabs, blood samples, the widest range of samples targeted by a procedure. Nonetheless, the experts recognised that the same approach (direct streaking onto plates and testing colonies) is not feasible for the analysis of foodstuffs, which relies on a liquid enrichment and a primary screening of the enriched sample. In this respect, and as mentioned above, it is not possible to harmonise fully the analyses of both sectors, whereas harmonisation is more easily achievable for characterization methods.
- ✓ This exercise led to the identification of a procedure to harmonise the detection of STEC in human samples that is currently proposed as an output of this task. Indeed, in the ranking, another methodology which refers to the same workflow as ISO TS 13136:2012, including the use of real time PCR, has been identified at the same rank as ISO TS 13136:2012, and is published (see Morabito et al, 2021 in the reference list in Annex 1).
- ✓ The method selected for STEC detection targets diarrhoeagenic *E. coli* (with the exception of enteroaggregative *E. coli*) and therefore can be applied for the detection of ETEC too.
- ✓ For STEC characterization, the group decided to recommend a conventional PCR-based method, which comprises the detection of all the targets specified in the above-mentioned criteria, including the detection of *eae* and *aggR* and the determination of the *stx* subtypes according to the protocols used in different laboratories operating in public health or the food/veterinary sectors, including the EURL for *E. coli*.
- ✓ For ETEC characterization, a gap in the protocols, particularly determining the presence of colonization factors, was highlighted. Only two methods detecting either *st* and *lt* or colonization factors have been identified, one based on real time PCR and the other on conventional PCR. The protocol for the detection of ETEC (real time based) includes primers (for *st* and *it*) that can also be used for characterization. Thus, the expert group suggested a PCR based protocol for characterization of ETEC that employs the primers for *st* and *lt* used in the detection method (so the laboratories are already equipped with the same reagents for the detection and characterization) and the primers for ETEC colonization factors indicated in the second PCR protocol mentioned above.
- ✓ The ease of implementation and the wider availability of required instruments have been a factor in recommending conventional PCR for both detection and typing, rather than real time PCR and WGS, which require expensive equipment and expertise in analysis. Nonetheless the group

of experts recognised the undeniable potentialities of more advanced technologies, such as real time PCR and WGS, which are already in use in several reference laboratories. It is likely that such technologies will become more widely used in laboratories working with detection and typing of microorganisms (particularly real time PCR).

The procedures developed are attached here as Annexes 6-8. Annex 11 consists in a document focusing on ETEC toxins nomenclature.

Revision and adaptability of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of STEC/ETEC

Alongside the ranking and identification of the protocols for the detection and typing of STEC and ETEC, an intensive search has been carried out in order to investigate the appropriate targets. During this process, several new subtypes of Stx have been described and published as part of the OH-Harmony-Cap project *i.e.* references 1-2 and 3-4. Similarly, more than 800 different alleles of the *eae* gene were found in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) databases and an international collaboration was established in order to revise and develop the associated nomenclature and new detection targets for both the *stx* and *eae* genes. Similar searches for the ST and LT genes in ETEC were conducted in order to get an overview of additional targets for the detection of all subtypes and variants of enterotoxins. In addition, primers for *aggR* have been updated and are now based on more than 200 *aggR* genes from clinical enteroaggregative *E. coli* (EAEC). Beta versions of sequence databases have been developed and are in process of being tested as well as revised PCR protocols for these targets. Preliminary results indicate that new omni detection primers can be developed and are being tested at SSI to be shared and compared with the ranked protocols for the final workshop of the OH-Harmony-Cap project.

WP4-T3-S2: Ranking of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

The basis for AMR determination is a pure culture, and this means that it is the same methods that are applied across the OH-sectors.

The protocols for **determination** of AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* are harmonised by several international bodies. ECDC has issued an EU protocol for harmonised monitoring of AMR in human *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* isolates (www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/eu-protocol-harmonised-monitoring-antimicrobial-resistance-human-salmonella-and-0). The monitoring of AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* from animals and food isolates is regulated by Decision 2020/1729 of 17 November 2020 on the monitoring and reporting of antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic and commensal bacteria and repealing Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32020D1729&from=EN>).

The ECDC method describes both the use of dilution-based to determine MIC and diffusion-based methods (disks and gradient strips) and refers to a large extent to the guidance from The European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing – EUCAST (www.eucast.org) on the practical

performance of AMR testing. The harmonised EU protocols further list and prioritize antimicrobials that *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* should be tested against for surveillance purposes.

The legislation on AMR in Decision 2020/1729 stipulates the use of broth microdilution based minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) methods and indicates the antimicrobials and the testing range that should be applied. The standard European protocol for broth microdilution (BMD) determination of MIC for *Salmonella* is the ISO 20776-1:2019 protocol: Susceptibility testing of infectious agents and evaluation of the performance of antimicrobial susceptibility test devices — Part 1: Broth micro-dilution reference method for testing the *in vitro* activity of antimicrobial agents against rapidly growing aerobic bacteria involved in infectious diseases. For *Campylobacter*, EUCAST recommends the same methodology with the application of Mueller Hinton broth supplemented with lysed horse blood β -NAD, and incubation under microaerophilic conditions to support the growth of *Campylobacter*. This method corresponds to the standard broth microdilution method issued by Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI): M45, 3rd edition: Methods for Antimicrobial Dilution and Disk Susceptibility Testing of Infrequently Isolated or Fastidious Bacteria. CLSI have also issued a standard that are used for animal isolates of *Campylobacter*: VET06: Methods for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of infrequently isolated or fastidious bacteria isolated from animals, 1st Edition, Jan. 2017.

According to EUCAST, the use of alternative MIC based methods, including proprietary methods, are allowed if the methods are validated against the EUCAST recommended ISO protocol following the ISO 20776-2:2021 standard: Susceptibility testing of infectious agents and evaluation of performance of antimicrobial susceptibility test devices — Part 2: Evaluation of performance of antimicrobial susceptibility test devices against reference broth micro-dilution.

Many laboratories use the commercial Sensititre® system from TREK Diagnostic Systems, Thermo Scientific, which is acknowledged by the EURL on AMR as an adequate method that can replace the use of the ISO method for *Salmonella* and CLSI method for *Campylobacter*.

Nine laboratories submitted information on the protocols used for AMR determination of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, of which seven submitted protocols for both species.

For *Campylobacter*, seven laboratories followed the principles of AMR determination stipulated in the Decision 2020/1729. Six of these laboratories used the commercial Sensititre® system from TREK Diagnostic Systems, Thermo Scientific, and one laboratory did not specify the applied method. Two laboratories reported that they performed disk diffusion test following the harmonised ECDC protocol. For *Salmonella*, six laboratories used the method stipulated in Decision 2020/1729 using the Sensititre® system. Two laboratories used disk diffusion and one laboratory did not specify the method that they used.

From the data on methods used for AMR testing in the laboratories participating in OH-Harmony-Cap project, it can be concluded that the laboratories are using the harmonised methods that are stipulated by ECDC and the EU legislation. Results generated by broth microdilution based methods and disk diffusion are comparable across sectors and if the quantitative results of MIC and disk diffusion are interpreted qualitative as resistant or sensitive (or non-wild-type or wild-type) using the same breakpoints or EUCAST epidemiological cut off values (ECOFFs), it is also possible to compare the qualitative results between methods. Both the harmonised ECDC protocol and the EU regulated protocols include breakpoints or ECOFFs for qualitative interpretations of MIC and inhibition zones.

The ranking of the laboratory protocols for determination of AMR was discussed at teleconferences and at the project meeting 9-11 November 2021, Dublin, Ireland. The protocols reported to be used by the OH-Harmony-Cap laboratories were all in line with the harmonised methods that are stipulated by ECDC and the EU legislation.

The features considered for the ranking of the collected AMR methods were:

- Specificity
- Sensitivity
- Method recognised as
- Ease of implementation
- Equipment and facilities
- Manhours
- Analysis duration
- Sample collection and storage (including transport)
- Can the targets used in the method easily be changed, eg primers in a PCR assay, new microscope
- Number of critical control points
- Complexity/preparation of sample
- Proficiency testing programmes
- Commercial kit
- Accredited method
- Ease in results interpretation
- Typing
- Comparability of results across the OH sector
- Cost per sample
- High throughput.

The results of the ranking are presented in Annex 5 for both dilution and diffusion based methods for both *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*. The ranking includes comments on each of the parameters that have been ranked.

Based on the common evaluation criteria the final scores of dilution and diffusion based methods were close (23 for dilution based methods and 25 for diffusion based methods), and both methods can be considered fit for the purpose. Both methods are already harmonised by international bodies (EUCAST, CLSI M45, ISO 20776-1:2019) and recommended by ECDC for surveillance in human isolates whereas for the mandatory monitoring of animal populations and fresh meat (Decision 2020/1729) MIC dilution based methods should be applied. The methods based on MIC using dilution-based methods are regarded as the best methods to determine AMR in both *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* for surveillance purposes. Generally, high throughput dilution-based methods require a larger laboratory set up as the MIC methods typically are based on proprietary methods that require investments in equipment and consumables. Disk- and gradient strip diffusion based methods are generally easier and cheaper to implement in the laboratories. It is also possible to set up BMD methods in a simple form, using microtiter plates, broths supplemented with relevant concentrations of antimicrobials, and manual reading of the MIC values. Ready to use microdilution plates are available commercially.

For all AMR methodologies it is important to stress that they should be performed in a standardised way in the laboratory and that proper controls, including control reference strains, always should be employed.

WP4-T3-S3: Ranking of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium* spp.

The parasite *Cryptosporidium* has high public health importance and is ranked among the top five parasites in the EU (Bouwknegt M, et al 2018). Despite the major public health implications, there is no harmonised method to test for *Cryptosporidium*. The collected protocols were distributed among experts from WP4. The protocols were sent mainly by the NRLs as well as the EURL, and altogether 11 research protocols on *Cryptosporidium* were evaluated. The team's work began in March 2021 with the aim to develop tools for the evaluation of research protocols. After several meetings and discussions, the group of experts prepared the tool for ranking the methods. A broad range of parameters were taken into account, including specificity, sensitivity, accreditation, ease of implementation, equipment and facilities, manhours, duration of analysis, sample collection, storage, flexibility of the method, critical control points, complexity, availability of proficiency testing (PT) programmes, commercial kits, accreditation, easy interpretation of results and comparability of results. The methods collected were divided into subgroups according to their principles in the following areas: 1) Sample preparation, 2) Microscopic detection, 3) Detection by PCR and 4) Typing. To check the efficiency of the evaluation tool developed (scoring table), the following exercise was performed. A group of six experts was selected. Each subgroup of methods areas was assessed independently by two experts. The collected results were discussed during a working group session of the project meeting 9-11 November 2021, Dublin, Ireland with a wider group of parasitologists among WP4 partners.

While discussing the results of the exercise, it was pointed out that there are gaps that prevent the correct assessment of the methods. The provided protocols were very diverse in terms of the contents of the method description. Some of them were complete and contained additional information, such as

validation results, while others were weaker in the description and did not allow evaluation of all criteria. The diversity of the content of the protocols was a significant obstacle in their assessment.

Lesson learned 1: While discussing the results of the evaluation, the need to conduct a questionnaire in parallel with the request of protocols was indicated. This questionnaire should include questions about the aim, matrix, method validation and the results of validation, accreditation, participation in PT, research and more (see Conclusions).

Regarding validation, the problem of the lack of a uniform approach to this issue and the lack of standards in this regard was also pointed out. The application of microbiological standards is often not available or impractical for parasites.

Lesson learned 2: During the discussion, a significant difficulty was indicated in recommending one method that could be used for various purposes only based on the evaluation exercise. During a virtual meeting in December 2021, it was established that due to the various matrices (e.g. faeces of infected humans or animals, soil, food, water, wastewater, contaminated surfaces or other sources) and to the variety of methodology applied depending on the needs, it was not possible to use one universal test method for all purposes. This exercise clearly highlighted the role and importance of a diagnostician in the analytical process. Therefore, the role and importance of training in the diagnosis of *Cryptosporidium* were emphasized.

Lesson learned 3: During the December 2021 virtual meeting, it was agreed that the developed evaluation tables gathering the collected methods may be useful in selecting the method implemented in the laboratory, however, it must be preceded by an analysis of the aims and applications of the selected method. Moreover, the importance of applying One Health approaches to the investigation of *Cryptosporidium* as a zoonosis was highlighted. Thus, both the direction of the study and the method used for the investigation are crucial.

The significance of the experience of the person performing this test is of particular importance for the final result. For this reason, training and possibly a decision tree might be helpful for the selection of diagnostic methods. This would be a more useful tool than scoring results. To facilitate this type of analysis, a decision tree, and training on how to use a combination of microscopic and molecular methods might be useful. Thus, the outcome of WP4-T3 for *Cryptosporidium* is not a ranking table but a decision tree (Annex 9) on which method to apply depending on the matrix, aim and capabilities.

The decision tree is an easy-to-read flowchart where each internal node signifies a decision and each branch represents a proposed course of action along with an indication at the end node of the final expected outcome or the possibility of further application of the outcome of the examination.

The elaborated decision tree comprehensively presents the current knowledge in the field of *Cryptosporidium* diagnostics, taking into account scientific and practical aspects. The presented flow-chart is the quintessence of a laboratory procedure taking into account the influence of various matrices (humans, animals, plants, environment, soil and sewage). Laboratory experience of experts working with this pathogen in humans and animals was used in the development of the scheme. The scheme also includes methods standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO Standard) and recommended by the EFSA. In addition, the developed tree is supported by protocol references (Annex 10)

Groups of experts:

WP4-T3-S1 leaders Rosangela Tozzoli (ISS), Nadia Boisen (SSI), team: Lin T. Brandal (NIPH), Catarina Flink (SLV), Silvia Herrera (ISCIII), Gro S. Johannessen (NVI), Angela Pista (INSA), Flemming Scheutz (SSI), Robert Soderlund (SVA).

WP4-T3-S2 Jeppe Boel (SSI), Isabelle Kempf (ANSES)

WP4-T3-S3 leaders Mirosław Rozycki (PIWET) and Mélanie GAY (ANSES), team: Gunita Deksnė (BIOR), Karin Troell (SVA), Fabio Tosini (ISS), Pikka Jokelainen (SSI), Rune Stensvold (SSI)

5. Conclusions

The activities conducted in WP4, considered only a subset of zoonotic pathogens, had the aim of proposing harmonised procedures applicable across sectors. The selected microorganisms can be considered as a proof of concept, and the approach used within the framework of this project on the model organisms under consideration can be used to define and propose harmonised procedures for additional pathogens.

The collection of protocols used in the reference laboratories operating in different sectors, allowed comparisons of the procedures applied for the detection and typing of the target microorganisms, and the identification of possible areas of harmonisation. This led to the definition of different strategies for the ranking of the protocols, depending on the pathogen considered, and different outputs were produced. The activities conducted also highlighted areas of improvement for the exercise itself. A way of better addressing some issues during the collection of the protocols would have been of great help for the subsequent activities. The administration of a questionnaire together with the request of the protocols would have been very useful. Questions proposed to the laboratories willing to share the protocols could include:

- What is the purpose of this method (routine analyses, official analyses, research...)?
- When and how do you use it?
- Did you validate/verify this method?
- How did you validate/verify it? Which samples for specificity, sensitivity?
- Did you use the microbiological validation or verification protocol (EN ISO 16140 series)?
(Especially important for parasites where no specific validation process exists)
- What is the specificity? The sensitivity?
- Is it quantitative or qualitative?
- What are the targets (specie(s), type(s)...)?
- Is it issued from a recognized organization (ISO, AFNOR, EURL...)?
- Is the purification/enrichment step compulsory or only used in specific occasions/matrices? [or] are all steps compulsory in any occasion/for any matrices? If no, please describe.
- Do you participate in proficiency testing (PTs) with this specific protocol?

The output of WP4 (proposed procedures and decision tree) will be shared with the networks that collaborated in the collection of protocols and will be applied in the activities foreseen in OH-Harmony-Cap WP5, concerning training through webinars and laboratory training.

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- ✓ Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES (Public Health and Vet/Food sectors)
- ✓ Public Health Wales, UK (Public Health)
- ✓ National Centre of Infectious and Parasitic Diseases, Bulgaria (Public Health Sector)
- ✓ National Public Health Centre, Hungary (Public Health)
- ✓ Central Veterinary Research Laboratory Ireland (Veterinary sector)
- ✓ Wageningen Bioveterinary Research WBVR, the Netherlands (Veterinary)
- ✓ Laboratory for Communicable diseases, Estonia (Public Health)

- ✓ National Hospital Iceland (Public Health)
- ✓ National Institute of Public Health, Czech Republic (Public Health)
- ✓ Laboratorio de Referencia de *E. coli* (LREC), Spain (Vet/Food safety sector)
- ✓ National Reference Laboratory Slovakia (Vet/Food safety sector)

Annexes:

Annexes 1-3: Evaluation tables of the protocols collected (institutes names anonymized)

Annex 4: Ranking table for STEC/ETEC (same anonymization used in the evaluation tables)

Annex 5: Ranking table for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

Annex 6-8: Harmonised procedures for STEC and ETEC

Annex 9-10: Decision Tree for detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium* spp. and list of proposed PCR tools for gp60

Annex 11: ETEC toxins nomenclature

Annex 1. Evaluation table of the protocols for the detection and characterisation of Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC) and Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC)

Protocol ID	Institute ID	PH/Vet/Food	Type of protocol (detection/typing)	Title	Reference(s)	Sample type(s)	Quantity of starting material	Principle of the method	Target(s)	Comments on target(s)	Short description of the Procedure (equipment or other specific reagents needed)	Comments on applicability in other labs	Additional comments
EC-1	A	Vet	D	Qualitative method for culture and IMS of VTEC O103	-	Animal faeces, overshoe samples, environmental samples, food	25 g solids or 1/10 volume of the pre-enrichment broth for liquids	Pre-enrichment, IMS, agglutination	STEC O103	-	Samples incubated at 41,5° C for 18-24 h in 225 ml mTSB with novobiocin 8 mg/L. IMS with Dynabeads EPEC/EHEC O103, transfer to three sheep blood agar plates with vancomycin and cefixime, incubated 37 °C for 18-24 h. Agglutination with SSI O103 sera on colonies w. haemolysis.	Yes, standard methods	PCR confirmation in EC_6
EC-2	A	Vet	D	Qualitative method for culture and IMS of VTEC O26	-	Animal faeces, overshoe samples, environmental samples, food	25 g solids or 1/10 volume of the pre-enrichment broth for liquids	Pre-enrichment, IMS, agglutination	STEC O26	-	Samples incubated at 41,5° C for 18-24 h in 225 ml mTSB with novobiocin 8 mg/L. IMS with Dynabeads EPEC/EHEC O26, transfer to CT-RMAC Rhamnose McConkey agar w. cefixime 0,05mg/l and potassium tellurite 1,25 mg/ml. Food samples to additional standard RMAC plate. Incubated 37 °C for 18-24 h. Agglutination with SSI O26 sera on pale colonies, confirm <i>E. coli</i> with indole test.	Yes, standard methods	PCR confirmation in EC_6
EC-3	A	Vet	D	Qualitative method for culture and IMS of VTEC O121	-	Animal faeces, overshoe samples, environmental samples, food	25 g solids or 1/10 volume of the pre-enrichment broth for liquids	Pre-enrichment, IMS, agglutination	STEC O121	-	Samples incubated at 41,5° C for 18-24 h in 225 ml mTSB. IMS with Abraxis <i>E. coli</i> O121, transfer to CT-RMAC Rhamnose McConkey agar w. cefixime 0,05mg/l and potassium tellurite 1,25 mg/ml incubated 37 °C for 18-24 h. One blue loopful used to repeat IMS. Beads to McConkey plates, incubated 37 °C for 18-24 h. Agglutination with SSI or Abraxis O121 sera on pale colonies, confirm <i>E. coli</i> with indole test.	Yes, standard methods	PCR confirmation in EC_6

EC-4	A	Vet	D	SVA method for VTEC O157 culture and VIP test Gold VTEC	-	Food, carcass swabs	25g food sample or one swab	Pre-enrichment, immunoprecipitation	STEC O157	-	Sample incubated at 41,5° C for 18-24 h in 225 ml mTSB with 1ml solution of 0.45g novobiocin in 100ml water added. Temperature allowed to drop to 25-37° C, stirred gently. 0.1 ml broth added to test well of VIP Gold EHEC device, device read after 15 min and interpreted (manufacturer instructions). Suspected pos. sample broths are analysed by IMS + PCR.	Uses an immunoprecipitation device	Intended to be combined with unspecified IMS protocol and PCR confirmation in EC_6
EC-5	A	Vet	D	Method for culture of E. coli and preparation of lysates for ETEC analysis	-	Faecal samples (pig), rectal swabs	Not specified	Culture	ETEC	-	Samples cultured on one bovine blood agar and one blue agar plate, incubated overnight at 37° C. Two colonies consistent with E. coli selected with preference for any showing haemolysis.	Yes, standard methods	PCR confirmation in EC_6
EC-6	A	Vet	D/T	Description of the PCR-methods used for VTEC and ETEC	LT, STaP, O91, O104, H4, O157: EURL VTEC; STb, F4, F5, F6, F18, F41: Frydendal 2001; ST1/2, O103, O111, O157: ISO/TS 13136: 2012; ST1/2: Perelle 2004, eae: Nielsen 2003; O113: Perelle 2003; O145: Fratamico 2011; O121: In-house	Colonies, enrichment broth	200 µl broth, colonies.	Real-time PCR	ETEC triplex [STaP,STb,LT] triplex [F4,F5,F6], duplex [F18,F41] STEC triplex [ST1, ST2, eae], O26, O91, O103, duplex [O104, H4], O111, O113, O121, O145, O157	-	Colonies in 100-500 µl nuclease-free water and boiled at 98-100°C for ten min. Lysates cooled and centrifuged at 13.000xg for 5 min, supernatant used as DNA template. Enrichment broths extracted with EZ1 DNA Tissue kit (Qiagen). PCR with PerfeCTa qPCR Toughmix and FAM/HEX/CY5 probe labels. Reaction volume 15 µl + 2 µl template, multiple probe and primer concentrations. Run on ABI 7500 Fast.	Yes, standard methods	-

EC-7	B	Vet/Food	T	Real-time multiplex PCR for detection of the aggR and aaiC genes of enteroaggregative E. coli (EAEC), of the lt, sth and stp genes of enterotoxigenic E. coli (ETEC), of the ipaH of enteroinvasive E. coli (EIEC)	EURL VTEC	DNA from E. coli extracted with MagNa Pure Compact or Chelex	2 µl extracted DNA	Real-time PCR	EAEC duplex [aggR, aaiC], ETEC triplex [lt, sth, stp], EIEC ipaH	-	PCR with LC Multiplex DNA Master and FAM/TAMRA/CY5/R6G probe labels. Reaction volume 18 µl + 2 µl template., primers 0,5µM probes 0,2µM. Run on LightCycler 480II	Yes, standard methods	-
EC-8	B	Vet/Food	D	Detection of verotoxin producing E. coli (VTEC) in goods subject to the LMSVG [transl. note: Austrian food safety and consumer protection law] and animal feed according to ISO/TS 13136	ISO/TS 13136:2012	Food, animal feed, environmental samples	25 g solids, 25 ml liquids	Pre-enrichment, real-time PCR, isolation, optional serogroup PCR followed by IMS	STEC, optional O26, O103, O111, O145 and O157	-	Samples mixed with 225ml mTSB with 16mg/l Novobiocin (meat) 12mg/l Acriflavin (dairy) or BPW (frozen samples, environmental samples). Solids run in stomacher for 2-3 min. Incubated at 41,5° C for 18-24 h, DNA extracted w. MagNA Pure Compact. PCR stx1/stx2 with LightCycler Fast Start DNA Master Kit and FAM/TAMRA probe labels. Reaction volume 18 µl + 2 µl template. For isolation, SMAC, CT-SMAC, and TBX plates streaked with stx-positive pre-enriched samples, and incubated overnight at 37° C. Lysates from primary streaks prepared with Chelex analysed with fourplex PCR for stx1, stx2, eae and E-hly. Analysis repeated on colony pools e.g. 5 colonies x 10 pools to isolate individual STEC. Optionally, stx-positive pre-enrichment samples or streaks analysed with PCR targeting O26, O103, O111, O145 and O157. IMS on positive samples with Captivate E. coli IMS kit for corresponding serotype.	Yes, standard methods	Refers to two separate PCR protocols for isolation step which were not provided
EC-9	C	Food	D	Qualitative detection of shiga toxin producing E. coli (STEC) in fresh plant-based food	Stx1: Sharma 1999; stx2, eae: Pavlovic 2010; IC: Anderson 2005	Fresh plant-based food other than sprouts	25 g	Pre-enrichment, real-time PCR, isolation	STEC	-	Samples mixed with 225ml BPW in stomacher for 1 min. Incubated 18 h with agitation at 37° C. 2x0.1 ml spread on TBX and incubated 18-24 h at 44° C. 1ml 0.9% NaCl added to the plates and growth suspended, 100 µl collected and diluted 1:10 in	Yes, standard methods	-

											water then heated to 95° C 10 min. 10k g 30 s centrifugation. PCR stx1/stx2/eae with QuantiTect Multiplex No ROX Mastermix. Reaction volume 20 µl + 2 µl template w. internal control. Multiple instrument types. For optional isolation, three 10-fold dilutions of pre-enrichment broth and TBX plate wash in 0.9% NaCl plated streaked in triplicate on TBX + optional CHROMagar. Incubated 18-24 h at 44° C. Ten colonies collected from each plate based on morphology, suspended in 200 µl water, thermal lysis and multiplex PCR as above.		
EC-10	C	Food	T	Real-time PCR for detection of shiga toxin producing E. coli	ISO/TS 13136:2012 Primers: Tzschoppe 2012	DNA from isolated E. coli	2 µl extracted DNA	real-time PCR	STEC duplex [eae, ehxA], duplex [stx1, stx2], duplex [nleB/stx2 e/f]		PCR with TaqMan Gene Expression Master Mix and FAM/VIC probe labels with IAC. Reaction volume 18 µl + 2 µl template., primers 0,5µM probes 0,2µM. Run on AB7500 or other instrument	Yes, standard methods	-
EC-11	C	Food	D	Detection and isolation of STEC from sprouts assisted by acid treatment	Verhaegen et al. 2016, Fedio et al. 2012, Lampart et al. 2020 ISO/TS 13136 (SPEC 10794):2013-04 Appendix F	Sprouts	25 g	Pre-enrichment, real-time PCR, isolation	STEC		Samples mixed with 225ml BPW in stomacher for 1 min. Incubated 18 h with agitation at 37° C. 1,3 ml centrifuged 12k g for 3 min, pellet resuspended in 1,3 ml TSB pH 2 and incubated 30 min room temp. Centrifuged again, pellet resuspended in 1,3 ml PBS. 0.1 ml spread on TBX and incubated 18-24 h at 44° C. 1ml 0.9% NaCl added to the plates and growth suspended. Lysis and PCR according to "house method" (EC_9). 1 ml suspension serially diluted in steps of 10 in PBS or 0.9 % NaCl to 10 ⁻³ . 100 µl plated on TBX and incubated 37 °C for 18-24 h. Suspected colonies selected according to DIN CEN ISO/TS 13136 (SPEC 10794):2013-04 Appendix F and analysed for STEC characteristics with "house methods".	Yes, standard methods	Lysis and PCR in EC_9
EC-12	D	Food	D	Shiga toxin producing E. Coli (STEC) – detection and isolation	ISO/TS 13136:2012 PCR eae Nielsen et al. 2003, stx1/stx2/O157/O26/	Food	25 g	Pre-enrichment, real-time PCR, isolation	STEC	-	25 g sample in 225 ml BPW or MTSB+N if background flora problematic or MTSB+A for dairy. Mixed in stomacher 1 min mid speed.	Yes, standard methods	Deviation from ISO/TS 13136:2012

					O111/O145 Perelle et al. 2004, O103 Perelle et al. 2005 O104/H4 EURL VTEC Acid treatment Fedio et al. 2012						Mix by hand for mincemeat to reduce free fat. Incubate 18-24 h at 37° C. DNA extracted from 200 µl broth with BioRobot EZ1 DNA Tissue Kit eluting in 100 µl. Heat tubes to 95° C 10 min. PCR with ABI TaqMan universal mix and FAM/VIC/HEX probe labels with IAC. Duplex stx1/IAC, all other singleplex. Reaction volume 20 µl + 5 µl template., variable primer/probe conc. Run on Roche Lightcycler. If serotype positive, IMS with Captivate O104 / Dynabeads for other serotypes. Direct culture if stx positive (parallel with IMS if also serotype positive): 10 µl broth on "relevant plates" (suggested: O157 - CT-SMAC, SMAC, mRBA; O26 - RMAC, TBX, CT-RMAC; O111/O145/O103/O104 - TBX, Chromagar STEC, mRBA.) # Optional acid treatment if background flora is problematic (to be combined w. IMS/direct culture): 1,5 ml broth centrifuged 12 000 x g 3 min. Pellet resuspended in 1,3 ml TSB pH 2. Room temp 30 min. Centrifuge 12 000 x g 3 min, resuspended in 1 ml PBS. 25 µL streaked on relevant plates. # Confirmation PCR preferably on minimum 50 colonies, crude lysates 95° C 10 min + centrifuge used directly for same PCR as above.		annealing temperatur 55 °C instead of 60 °C Refers to optional non-accredited immunoblot protocol 12-m242 (not provided)
EC-13	E	Vet	D	Isolation using IMS				Pre-enrichment, IMS	STEC O157, O26, O145, O111, O103, O55	-	Magnetic beads specific for O157, O26, O145, O111, O103 (Dynabead; Dynal) and O55 (prepared in-house) are used for IMS selective enrichment of these serotypes from enriched samples. 1. Samples are enriched for 6h at 37°C in buffered peptone water for all serotypes. An enrichment broth is prepared for samples (faeces environmental swabs etc) at a dilution of 1:10 (e.g. 1g faeces + 9ml BPW) 2. IMS performed for the serotype of interest with the appropriate magnetic beads using an automated bead retriever. 3. IMS beads are plated onto CT-SMAC, CT-RMAC or Chromagar	Yes, standard methods	Provided as a short summary

											ECC (Media used is dependent on the target). 4. Plates are incubated at 37°C overnight and slide agglutination used along with colony PCR to identify target serotype. Suspect colonies are checked by slide agglutination and colony PCR to confirm the presence of VT and eae genes. Serogroup-specific PCR is used to confirm the target serogroup is present.		
EC-14	E	Vet	D	Identification by slide agglutination				Agglutination	STEC	-	Latex agglutination is carried out with specific reagents from Oxoid for most serogroups with the exception of O55 which uses ImmuLex (SSI diagnostics).	Yes, standard methods	Provided as a short summary
EC-15	E	Vet	T	Detection of E. coli virulence factors using PCR.	Casey and Bosworth (J Vet Diagn. Invest. 2009)	DNA samples	3 µl extracted DNA	Conventional PCR	ETEC Multiplex 1: STaP (estA) K99 (fanA) LTb subunit (eltB) F18 (fedA) F41 (fedA subunit) ETEC Multiplex 1: STaP (estA) K99 (fanA) LTb subunit (eltB) F18 (fedA) Stx2e (A subunit) Multiplex 2: STb (estB), K88 (faeG),	Markers for porcine oedema ETEC	PCR with Qiagen multiplex master mix, HotStarTaq master mix or equivalent. Reaction volume 22 µl + 3 µl template. Products run on 2% agarose gel 60-90min at 150 volts in 1XTBE buffer. Visualise gel after soaking in ethidium bromide solution 30min.	Yes, standard methods, requires facilities for gel electrophoresis	-

									987P (fasA)				
EC-16	E	Vet	T	PCR detection of E. coli virulence genes VT1, VT2, and eae.	Kagkli et al. 2011, Nielsen & Andersen 2003	DNA samples	2 µl extracted DNA	Real-time PCR	STEC stx1, stx2, eaeA	-	PCR with QuantiTect Multiplex PCR (No ROX) and FAM/HEX/TEX/Rd probe labels. Reaction volume 23 µl + 2 µl template. Run on Agilent Aria or MXpro Stratagene.	Yes, standard methods	Two primer/probe sets for stx1 and stx2 in the protocol, unclear if both used
EC-17	E	Vet	T	Real-time PCR for the detection of Shiga-toxin producing E. coli (STEC) associated O-antigens: O26, O157, O111, O145, O103 and O55.	DebRoy, C. et al. (2005) Perelle, S et al (2004) Fratamico, PM. et al (2011)	DNA samples	2 µl extracted DNA	Real-time PCR	STEC O26, O157, O111, O145, O103, O55	-	PCR with LC Multiplex DNA Master and FAM/HEX/CY5/TEX/Rd probe labels. Reaction volume 18 µl + 2 µl template., primers 0,5µM probes 0,2µM. Run on LightCycler 480II.	Yes, standard methods	-

EC-18	F	PH	T	<i>E. coli</i> PCR	Al-Ajmi et al., 2006. Wirth et al., 2006. Baker et al., 2003.	<i>E. coli</i> isolates	Lysate from 1 colony	Determine the presence of a set of <i>E. coli</i> virulence genes and if the isolate is a O157:H7	<i>eae</i> (intimin), <i>ehxA</i> (haemolysin), <i>stx₁</i> , <i>stx₂</i> and <i>stx_{2c}</i> (Shiga toxin), O157-antigen, H7-antigen,	STEC	Conventional PCR tests and gel electrophoreses are performed to demonstrate the presence of the target genes.	Yes, standard methods, requires facilities for gel electrophoresis	-
EC-19	F	PH	T	Typing <i>E. coli</i>	Joensen et al., 2015.	(Shiga toxin-producing) <i>E. coli</i> isolates	Single colony	Determine the <i>E. coli</i> serotype from NGS data	O-antigen, H-antigen	-	Enrich the colony in a broth, perform DNA extraction from a part of the enrichment, NGS analysis, quality trim the generated reads and assemble them using a publicly available pipeline, from the assembly determine the <i>E. coli</i> serotype <i>in silico</i> using a publicly available pipeline.	Requires facilities for NGS and bioinformatics	-
EC-20	G	PH/Vet	D/T	Primary reception of faecal specimens	None given for all non- <i>E. coli</i> . For diarrhoeagenic <i>E. coli</i> (DEC):	extract-agar stab, plateculture, transport medium, blood sample, faeces, Stuart's medium, E.swab, Faecal-swab,intestinal biopsy, tissue specimens or freeze dried culture	Any volume or quantity	Plating on differential selective media, incubation temperatures and oxygen levels	<i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> , <i>Shigella</i> , <i>Yersinia</i> , <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> , <i>V. cholerae</i> , <i>C. perfringens</i> , <i>Bacillus cereus</i> , EPEC/ EIEC/ ETEC/ AEEC, <i>C. difficile</i> ,	DEC targets are up for revision. Should also include <i>aggR</i>	Media used: Blue plate TSA- Blood plate 5% SSI Enteric medium (9cm) plate SSI Enteric medium (14cm) plate CCDA plate (black) plate ChromID-plate CDIF plate VRE-plate ESBL-plate EYA-plate Na-azid-plate Sabouraud plate pH 4,0 Cholerae plate Beef extract broth Selenite 0,6%	Primarily in house media and methods	Complete flow of specimens from primary specimen to WGS on almost all positive specimens

EC-21	G	PH/Vet	D	Multiplex PCR, <i>E. coli</i>	Modified from Persson 2007	Selected colonies	Minimum of three colonies	PCR	DEC: STEC/EP EC/ EIEC/ ETEC/ AECC,	Original reference did not cover <i>stx2f</i> , for which additional primers have been added.	PCRs were performed in a total reaction volume of 25 IL containing 1 · PCR buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, 10 mM KCl, 5 mM (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ , pH 8.3), 2.6 mM MgCl ₂ , 260 IM each of dATP, dCTP and dGTP, 520 IM dUTP, 0.15 U of UNG (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA), 1.25 U of Taq polymerase (FastStart; Roche Diagnostics), and the 16 primers shown in Table 1 in the listed concentrations (DEC Primer Mix; SSI Diagnostica, Hillerød, Denmark). These included a primer pair for the 16S rDNA gene as a positive internal PCR control. Template volumes were 5 IL when PCRs were performed with bacterial cultures and stool samples extracted with the QIAamp DNA Stool Kit, and 1 IL when stool samples were extracted with the KingFisher mL system. Amplification conditions comprised 94C for 6 min, followed by 35 cycles of 94C for 50 s, 57C for 40 s and 72C for 50 s, and finally 72C for 3 min. Amplicons were analysed by electrophoresis on agarose 1.5%w/v gels using standard conditions, followed by staining with ethidium bromide.	Can be used in any diagnostic laboratory with a PCR facility	Need of update with new primers in order to cover all the target genes: <i>stx1</i> , <i>eae</i> , <i>stx2</i> , <i>estah</i> (Human ST, STIh), <i>estap</i> (Porcine ST, STIp), <i>eltI</i> , <i>ipaH</i> , and positive control 16S rDNA.
EC-22	G	PH/Vet	T	Identification of three <i>stx1</i> and seven <i>stx2</i> subtypes of Shiga toxin encoding genes of <i>E. coli</i> by conventional PCR amplification	Scheutz et al 2014 updated on SSI.DK: stx detection subtyping protocol rev 7 (ssi.dk)	PCR (<i>stx1</i> and/or <i>stx2</i>) positive colonies and/or boiled culture from these.	Standard PCR in total volume of 20 µl: 2.5 µl H ₂ O § 10 µl Mastermix (HotStarTaq, Qiagen), 1.25 µl of each of two primers (STOCK solution of primers is 5 µM) § 5 µl supernatant of boiled lysate (STOCK)	PCR	<i>stx1a</i> , <i>stx1c</i> , <i>stx1d</i> , <i>stx2a</i> , <i>stx2b</i> , <i>stx2c</i> , <i>stx2d</i> , <i>stx2e</i> , <i>stx2f</i> and <i>stx2g</i>	Not validated for new stx subtypes <i>stx1e</i> , <i>stx2h</i> , <i>stx2i</i> , <i>stx2j</i> , <i>stx2k</i> and <i>stx2l</i> – see reference (3)	Triplex for <i>stx1</i> subtypes and single PCR for subtyping of <i>stx2</i> subtypes.	Universal	Update needed for new stx subtypes <i>stx1e</i> , <i>stx2h</i> , <i>stx2i</i> , <i>stx2j</i> , <i>stx2k</i> and <i>stx2l</i> – see reference (3).

EC-23	H	PH/Vet/Food	D	Detection and isolation of STEC from clinical samples	Perelle et al 2004 (stx1/2, rfbEO157, wzxO26, wbdO111, ihp1 O145), Nielsen et al 2003 (eaeA), Perelle et al 2005 (wzxO103)	Human faeces, faecal swabs, mixed and pure bacterial cultures	Enrichment is made up with 1 g of faecal specimen diluted 1/10 in TSB. A 1 µl loopful bacteria for the bacterial cultures in 10 ml TSB. Swab is put in 10 ml TSB.	Molecular biology and microbiological techniques: Enrichment, Real Time PCR screening, plating and colonies confirmation	All STEC, and the determination of certain STEC serogroups (top-5)	Same targets/primers and probes of ISO TS 13136. The Real Time PCR primers and probe for stx2 do not target stx2f subtype	Faecal specimen or bacterial cultures inoculated in TSB and grown overnight at 37°C. The day after DNA is extracted from 1 ml and Real Time PCR targeting STEC virulence genes (stx1/stx2 and eae) is carried out. In case of positivity to both stx and eae top-5 serogroups Real Time PCR is run as screening too. When the presence of stx is detected, isolation is attempted. The overnight culture is streaked onto media such as TBX or RMAC (CT-SMAC or RMAC if the presence of STEC O26 or STEC O157 is suspected, respectively) and single colonies are tested again for the presence of STEC-associated genes.	Yes, standard methods	The approach is detecting all STEC and not only certain types. The initial screening for STEC allows the further testing for the confirmation of the colonies only in the positive samples.
EC-24	H	PH/Vet/Food	D	Detection of free Shiga toxin in faecal samples		Human faeces	1 g or 1 mL (if liquid) of the faecal sample in 1 mL of sterile saline solution	Cellular biology: Observation of the cytopathic effect induced by the Stx on Vero cells	Free Shiga Toxin present in faecal specimen	The approach of this method allows the detection of all Shiga toxin subtypes	The faecal sample is added to 1 mL of sterile saline solution in a 1.5 mL tube and mixed thoroughly, centrifuged and filtered. The supernatant is then inoculated (three dilutions) onto Vero cells monolayers and incubated at 37°C in CO ₂ atmosphere. The inoculated cells monolayer are observed for detecting the appearance of a cytopathic effects (CPE) after 24, 48 and 72 h to monitor the progression of the CPE. If needed (i.e. cytopathic effect not clear), the specificity of the CPE by applying serum neutralisation test.	The use of the Vero cell assay (VCA) requires the expertise in cellular biology, the morphology of the Stx-mediated cytotoxic effect, and neutralisation experiments with anti-Stx1 and/or anti-Stx2 antibodies to confirm the specificity of the observed cytotoxicity	The assay is very sensitive and can detect the presence of the free faecal toxin after the bacterium has been cleared following e.g. an antibiotic treatment.

EC-25	H	PH/Vet/Food	D	Detection of antibodies against STEC LPS in patients' sera using ELISA		Human serum	Serum sample (a few microliters are necessary)	ELISA	Antibodies against O157, O26, O103, O111, O145 LPSs	The method describes the screening of the presence of Antibodies against a limited number of LPS is screened, but the same procedure could be extended to other serogroups too.	The wells of an ELISA microplate are added with reference LPS (extracted previously) and let adhere overnight at 37°C. The serum sample is diluted 1:500 and 1:1000 with PBS and added to the wells sensitized with the reference LPS. positive and negative controls for LPS antigens and serum samples are added at each test. Incubate at 37°C for 90 min. The serum is removed and the wells are washed twice with ELISA buffer. Then detection of antibodies linked to the wells is made (using anti-human total IgG conjugated with alkaline phosphatase added with the substrate) The plate is then read with a spectrophotometer at $\lambda=405\text{nm}$ after 15 min and 30 min of incubation at the dark: the OD405 reads are compared with the controls to assess the presence of antibodies against specific LPS.	The lab should have experience with ELISA assays: for instance the working dilution of LPS are to be determined empirically	The test may be useful in case the detection of STEC in clinical specimen is not achieved for instance in case of antibiotic treatment. The spectrum of LPS is restricted to those serogroup mainly associated to HUS. The timing of the blood sample collection may influence the results (e.g. too early for the production of IgG)
EC-26	H	PH/Vet/Food	T	Identification of the VTEC serogroups mainly associated with human infections by conventional PCR amplification of O-associated genes	Bielaszewska M et al 2011; DebRoy C et al 2005; Li Y et al 2006; Liu Y et al 2007; Monday SR et al 2007; Paton AW and Paton JC 1999; Perelle S et al 2004	STEC strains	A single colony of STEC strain	Molecular biology: PCR	genes associated with STEC serogroups O26, O45, O55, O91, O103, O104, O111, O113, O121, O128, O145, O146, and O157	genes associated with the serogroups of STEC strains mainly reported from STEC infections	DNA template is prepared by boiling single colonies. PCR is carried out, some targets may be amplified also in multiplex PCR. Gel electrophoresis to assess the amplification results.	Yes, standard methods	The method describes the detection of 13 serogroups, those frequently associated with STEC infections in humans. The same approach can be applied for the detection of

													other serogroups and the method can be enlarged to include new/emerging STEC serogroups
EC-27	H	PH/Vet/Food	T	Identification of the subtypes of Verocytotoxin encoding genes (vtx) of Escherichia coli by conventional PCR	Scheutz et al. 2012	STEC strains	A single colony of STEC strain	Molecular biology: PCR	Genes encoding Stx1a, Stx1c, Stx1d, Stx2a, Stx2b, Stx2c, Stx2d, Stx2e, Stx2f, Stx2g	Genes associated with ten stx subtypes. New subtypes have been described in recent years.	A bacterial culture originating from an overnight culture in TSB is diluted (25 µl of the culture added to 975 µl of MilliQ water) and boiled for 15 minutes. After centrifugation the supernatant is collected and 5 µl is used as template for PCR reactions. PCR and gel electrophoresis.	Yes, standard methods	The PCRs amplification of the targets described require particular attention and the use of a Taq polymerase reducing the amplification of non-specific DNA regions (such as a Hot Start Taq polymerase) shall be used.

EC-28	H	PH/Vet/Food	D	Detection of <i>Escherichia coli</i> producing the Stx2f subtype by Real-Time PCR		Foodstuff	25 g of food	Molecular biology (Real Time PCR and PCR) and microbiology	Stx2f coding gene	The target Stx2f is excluded from ISO TS 13136 and the procedure means to give the possibility to test food items for the presence of such gene too, in case of need	Food sample is enriched in the broth indicated in ISO TS 13136, then DNA extracted for the purpose of carrying out the ISO TS 13136 screening can be further investigated by Real time PCR for the detection of Stx2f. In case of positivity in the screening, the enrichment broth is seminated onto MacConkey agar or TBX plates or any other media suitable for <i>E. coli</i> isolation. Up to 50 isolated colonies with typical <i>E. coli</i> morphology are collected and tested by conventional PCR for the presence of stx2f gene/Scheutz et al. 2012)	Yes, standard methods	The same flux of ISO TS 13136 is applied in this method (screening and confirmation of single colonies). Moreover the Real Time PCR designed for Stx2f coding gene can be also applied to characterize isolated <i>E. coli</i> strains
EC-29	H	PH/Vet/Food	T	Identification of the STEC serogroups mainly associated with human infections by Real-Time PCR amplification of O-associated genes	Perelle et al., 2004, USDA, 2012, Perelle et al., 2005, Bugarel et al., 2010, Lin et al., 2011	STEC strains	STEC strain	Molecular biology (Real Time PCR and PCR)	genes associated with STEC serogroups O26, O45, O55, O91, O103, O104, O111, O113, O121, O128, O145, O146, and O157	genes associated with the serogroups of STEC strains mainly reported from STEC infections	DNA is extracted from a pure culture of STEC (either from an overnight culture or from solid medium), and Real Time PCRs are carried out	Yes, standard methods	The method is based on the 5' nuclease PCR assay, and compared to the PCR-based technique, provides additional specificity through the use of the probe in addition to the primers

EC-30	H	PH/Vet/Food	T	Molecular typing of VTEC strains isolated from food, feed and animals	Available at https://www.efsa.europa.eu/it/supporting-publication/2014 Caprioli A. et al EFSA supporting publication 2014	STEC strains	STEC strain	Molecular biology: Pulsed Field Gel Electrophoresis (PFGE), molecular typing method based on the restriction of the bacterial genome with rare cutting enzyme to generate pulsotypes	Bacterial genome	-	A pure colony of STEC is streaked on nutrient agar and incubated overnight at 37°C. The bacterial culture is then removed and suspended in a buffer (CSB). The cell suspension is added with proteinase K and embedded in agarose and treated (sarcosyl and proteinase K in water bath at 50-55°C for 2h, followed by washes in water and TE at 50-55°C) for extracting the DNA. A section of the plug mold containing the DNA is restricted with XbaI at 37°C for 3 hours and then loaded on the gel for the PFGE. After the run (lasting 19 hours in a specific electrophoresis apparatus), the gel is stained in ethidium bromide and the image acquired and analysed with BioNumerics software. It is necessary to include in specific wells of the gel XbaI-restricted Salmonella Braenderup, for normalizing the run. The result consists in a pulsotype, DNA bands profile, per each strain which is considered a fingerprint.	The laboratory shall be equipped with specific instruments for the Pulsed field electrophoresis	PFGE has been the gold standard for STEC over the past years. Nevertheless, the procedure is quite time consuming and labour intensive, and is now being overcome as the WGS.-based typing techniques are evolving more and more.
EC-31	H	PH/Vet/Food	D	Detection of Enterotoxigenic Escherichia coli in food by Real Time PCR amplification of the <i>lt</i> , <i>stx</i> , and <i>stx</i> genes, encoding the heat-labile and heat-stable enterotoxins	Liu et al., 2013	Foodstuff	25 g or 25 ml of food	Molecular biology (Real Time PCR and PCR) and microbiology	<i>lt</i> , <i>stx</i> , and <i>stx</i> genes	ETEC toxins coding genes, no genes involved in colonization targeted	Food sample is enriched in BPW overnight, then DNA extracted for the purpose of carrying out the Real time PCR for the detection of the genes coding for the major ETEC toxins, <i>Stx</i> , <i>Stx</i> and <i>LT</i> . In case of positivity in the screening, the enrichment broth is seminated onto MacConkey agar or TBX plates or any other media suitable for <i>E. coli</i> isolation. Up to 50 isolated colonies with typical <i>E. coli</i> morphology are collected and tested by the same Real Time PCR for confirming the presence of the target virulence genes	The procedure can be easily applied in labs equipped with both molecular biology and microbiology tests.	-

EC-34	J	PH	D	Detection of enterohaemorrhagic E. coli (ehec) by real-time PCR	Perelle et al. 2004, CRL E. coli	DNA samples, lysates	Unspecified	Real-time PCR	STEC (stx1, stx2, stx2f), O157 + H7	Includes stx2f	Reactions set up with QIAgility or manually, PCR with TaqMan Fast Universal PCR Master mix and FAM probe labels.	Yes, standard methods	PCR reaction setup volumes specified in internal system 'SmiOrganizer' (not provided)
EC-35	J	PH	D/T	Serotyping of ehec by real-time PCR	Perelle et al. 2004, CRL E. coli, Fratamico 2011, SVA in-house	DNA samples, lysates	2 µl extracted DNA	Real-time PCR	O26, O55, O91, O103, O111, O113, O121, O145	-	Reactions set up with QIAgility or manually, PCR with TaqMan Fast Universal PCR Master mix and FAM probe labels. Reaction volume 13 µl + 2 µl template. Run on ABI StepOne instrument.	Yes, standard methods	-
EC-36	J	PH	D	Working solutions for lysis buffer for gram positive and gram negative bacteria	-	NA	NA	Buffer preparation	STEC	-	Cell Lysis Buffer for gram negative bacteria: 50mM Tris, 50mM EDTA, 1% Sarcosyl (CLB) ; Cell Lysis Buffer with 4M Urea for EHEC: CLB (as above) 100 mL, Urea 24 g	Yes, standard methods	-
EC-37	J	PH	T	DNA extraction for whole genome sequencing	-	Colonies	1-2 loops	DNA extraction	STEC	-	Colonies suspended in 180 µL CLB + 4M urea with proteinase K, incubated 58 °C, 1 h. 2 µL RNaseA 100 mg/mL added, extraction with PSS MagLEAD, 100 µL elution volume. Quantification with Qubit, optional purity check with Nanodrop.	Specific automated DNA extraction system	-
EC-38	J	PH	T	Whole genome sequencing of enterohaemorrhagic E. coli (ehec).	Joensen et al. 2014, SeroTypeFinder	DNA samples	Not specified	Whole genome sing	STEC	-	DNA extracted and sequenced (IonTorrent) according to standard protocols. Data are analysed by an in-house pipeline combining cluster analysis, MLST, ESBL detection, virulence gene and serotype determination tools based on VirulenceFinder and SeroTypeFinder (CGE)	Uses an in-house data analysis pipeline	Refers to separate protocol for NGS laboratory work

EC-39	J	PH	D	Handling of gastrointestinal pathogenic bacteria	-	Fecal samples, cultures	-	Culture, IMS	STEC, O157, O145, O111, O103, O26, O121	-	Samples grown on SMAC plates, if culture impure optionally on CHROMagar, CT-SMAC or RMAC. DNA extracted for WGS as EC_FOHM.4, for PCR lysates one colony boiled in 100 µL PBS. To identify STEC in impure cultures PCR analysis of streaks, individual colonies (after WGS on impure cultures) or pools of 10 colonies (mixed culture on plates). IMS optional e.g. outbreaks, HUS-cases: Dynabeads anti- E. coli O157, O145, O111, O103, O26, O121	Yes, standard methods	-
EC-40	K	PH	T	Identification of Unconventional Intestinal Pathogenic Escherichia coli Isolates Expressing Intermediate Virulence Factor Profiles by Using a Novel Single-Step Multiplex PCR	Müller et al. 2007	Bacterial strains	-	PCR	<i>uidA</i> , <i>escV</i> , <i>bfpB</i> , <i>stx1</i> , <i>stx2</i> , <i>elt</i> , <i>estIa</i> , <i>estIb</i> , <i>invE</i> , <i>astA</i> , <i>aggR</i> , and <i>pic</i> ,	The LEE gene <i>escV</i> , has not been studied as well as <i>ee</i> . Both <i>astA</i> and <i>pic</i> have been found in non-diarrhoeagenic E.coli strains. <i>ipaH</i> is increasingly being used to detect EIEC.	Multiplex PCR was performed in 200 µl reaction tubes with a 25 µl reaction mixture consisting of 2 U of Taq DNA polymerase (Segetic, Borken, Germany), 84 mM Tris HCl (pH 8.5), 2.1 mM MgCl ₂ , 50 mM KCl, 14 mM 2-mercaptoethanol, 0.14% Triton X-100, 0.3 mM each deoxynucleoside triphosphate, and PCR primers at the concentrations listed in Table 1 of reference	Can be used in any diagnostic laboratory with a PCR facility	-

EC-41	L	PH	D	Detection of Escherichia coli virulence factors	Fujioka et al,2013	<i>E. coli</i> isolates	Single colony	Conventional PCR	<i>eae</i> , <i>aggR</i> , <i>elt</i> , <i>estp</i> , <i>invE</i>		DNA extraction: by automatic systems (NUCLISENS easyMAG or EMAG, Biomerieux) or by spin-column based purification kit (final elution: 50 µl). PCR was performed in a total reaction volume of 25µl. The reaction mix was prepared according to the manufacturer's recommendations of the polymerase used (HotStarTaq master mix or equivalent) and includes 0.2µl of each primer (stock solution in µM: <i>eae</i> -25, <i>aggR</i> -20, <i>elt</i> -10, <i>estp</i> -50, <i>invE</i> -50) and 5µl (1:10 dilution) of DNA. Amplification conditions: 94°C for 5 min, 35 cycles of 94°C for 1 min 15 s, 55.5°C for 1 min 45 s, 72°C for 2 min, and finally 72°C for 4 min. Amplicons were analysed by gel electrophoresis (2-2.25% agarose in TBE 0.5x).	Yes, standard methods	
EC-42	L	PH	D	Detection of verotoxins in E. coli by multiplex PCR	WHO Collaborating Centre SSI - Identification of three <i>vtx1</i> and seven <i>vtx2</i> subtypes of Verocytotoxin encoding genes of E. coli by conventional PCR amplification.	<i>E. coli</i> isolates	Single colony	Conventional PCR	<i>stx1</i> , <i>stx2</i>		DNA extraction: automatic systems (NUCLISENS easyMAG or EMAG, Biomerieux) or spin-column based purification kit (final elution: 50 µl). PCR was performed separately for <i>stx1</i> and <i>stx2</i> . Each mix (reaction volume: 20µl) contains 10µl of HotStarTaq master mix (Quiagen), 5µl of each primer (stock solution: 5 µM) and 5µl (1:10 dilution) of DNA. Amplification conditions: 95°C for 15 min, 35 cycles of 94°C for 50 s, 60°C for 50 s, 72°C for 1 min, and finally 72°C for 3 min. Amplicons were analysed by gel electrophoresis (2-2.25% agarose in TBE 0.5x).	Yes, standard methods	
EC-43	L	PH	T	Detection of verotoxins in E. coli by multiplex PCR	WHO Collaborating Centre SSI - Identification of three <i>vtx1</i> and seven <i>vtx2</i> subtypes of Verocytotoxin encoding genes of E. coli by conventional PCR amplification.	<i>E. coli</i> isolates	Single colony	Conventional PCR	<i>stx1a</i> , <i>stx1c</i> , <i>stx1d</i> , <i>stx2a</i> , <i>stx2b</i> , <i>stx2c</i> , <i>stx2d</i> , <i>stx2e</i> , <i>stx2f</i> , <i>stx2g</i>		Subtyping PCR was performed as a triplex for <i>stx1</i> and single for <i>stx2</i> , according the conditions presented at reference(s). Amplification conditions: 95°C for 15 min, 35 cycles of 94°C for 50 s, 64°C for 40 s, 72°C for 1 min, and finally 72°C for 3 min.	Yes, standard methods	Subtyping is performed only in <i>stx1</i> and/or <i>stx2</i> positive cases

EC-44	L	PH	D	Detection of pathogenic Escherichia coli - amplification of the main virulence genes by PCR in strains	EU-RL VTEC_Method_01_R ev 0; Campos et al,2015; Fujioka et al, 2013; Boisen et al, 2012; Nguyen et al, 2005;Aranda et al,2004; Schmidt et al, 2000; ISO 13136: 2012	E. coli isolates	Single colony	Conventional PCR	<i>astA</i> , <i>aaIC</i> , <i>aggR</i> , <i>ipaH</i> , <i>eltB</i> , <i>estA</i> , <i>eae</i> , <i>stx1</i> , <i>stx2</i> , <i>stx2f</i>		Colonies were boiled for 10 min, cooled, and centrifuged at 13.000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant is used as DNA template. Ten single PCRs were performed, with different mixtures and thermal profiles. References associated to each specific gene PCR conditions: <i>astA</i> , <i>aaIC</i> , <i>aggR</i> - adapted from Boisen et al, 2012; <i>ipaH</i> - Aranda et al,2004; <i>eltB</i> , <i>estA</i> - adapted from Campos et al,2015; Fujioka et al, 2013; Nguyen et al, 2005; <i>eae</i> - ISO 13136: 2012; <i>stx1</i> , <i>stx2</i> - ISO 13136: 2012; <i>stx2f</i> - adapted from Schmidt et al, 2000.	Yes, standard methods. However is a time-consuming protocol	Protocol used by the Department of Food and Nutrition. Difficult to resume the several PCR reactions mix and conditions.
EC-45	L	PH	D	Detection and identification of Verocytotoxigenic Escherichia coli (VTEC) - amplification of <i>stx1/2</i> and <i>eae</i> genes and genes associated with the serogroups by Real-Time PCR	ISO 13136: 2013; ISO 16654; - EU-RL VTEC_Method_02_R ev 0	Food, animal feed, environmental samples	25 g; swab/cloth/sponge	Pre-enrichment, real-time PCR, IMS, isolation	Detection of <i>stx</i> and <i>eae</i> genes and determination of some STEC serogroups (O26, O111, O45, O145, O121, O103 and O157:H7)		Enrichment of homogenized samples in BPW (1/10 dilution) at 37°C or mTSB at 41°C (for O157) for 18-24h. Use of 1 ml for DNA extraction with the Kit EZ1 DNA Tissue (Quiagen) or the QIAamp DNA Mini kit. Real Time PCR targeting STEC-associated <i>stx1/stx2</i> and <i>eae</i> (iQ-Check STEC VirX) is carried out. In case of positivity, real time PCR targeting O26, O111, O45, O145, O121, O103 and O157:H7 (iQ-Check STEC SerO) is running. Isolation is attempted using serogroup specific enrichment (IMS with Dynabeads kit) and the overnight culture is streaked onto media such as TBX or CT-SMAC and incubated overnight at 37° C. Pools of 10 colonies are tested for the presence of STEC-associated genes. If positive, extraction and PCR of individuals colonies were performed.	Yes, standard methods	

EC-46	L	PH	D	Detection of enterotoxigenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> - amplification of the <i>lt</i> and <i>stx</i> genes, encoding the heat-labile and heat-stable enterotoxins by PCR	EU-RL VTEC_Method_08_Rev 0; Campos et al, 2015; Fujioka et al, 2013; Nguyen et al, 2005	Food, animal feed, environmental samples	25 g; swab/cloth/sponge	Pre-enrichment, conventional PCR, isolation	<i>e1B, estA</i>		Enrichment of homogenized samples in BPW (1/10 dilution) at 37°C for 18-24h. Use of 1 ml for DNA extraction with the Kit EZ1 DNA Tissue (Qiagen) or the QIAamp DNA Mini kit. PCR adapted from references (volume of 25 µl) contains 2 µl of template, 1.5 µl MgCl ₂ , 0.5 µl dNTPs (at 2 µM), 0.75 µl primers (at 10 µM), 5 µl Taq buffer, 0.13 µl Taq (at 5u). Amplifications conditions: 94°C for 4 min, 35 cycles of 94°C for 1 min, 55°C for 1 min, 72°C for 1 min, and finally 72°C for 4 min. Isolation is attempted from enriched culture on TBX or CT-SMAC overnight at 37° C. Postive enrichment broths were screened (5 pools of 10 colonies) by the same PCR.	Yes, standard methods	
EC-47	M	Food	D	Method A - Detection of STEC O157	Chapman et al (1994)	Food	25 g solid	Pre-enrichment, IMS, isolation, conventional PCR	<i>stx1, stx2, eae-γ1, O157, H7,</i>		Enrichment of homogenized samples in 225 ml BPW with vancomycin, cefixime and cefsulodin at 37°C for 6h. IMS with specific Dynabeds is performed according the manufacturers and Chapman et al (1994). Isolation is attempted in agar MACSTC, 37°C/18 h (A-1) and in agar MACS, 37°C/18 h (A-2). PCR for <i>stx</i> and <i>eae-γ1</i> genes and for O157 and H7s antigens is performed. In positive cases (for at least one gene), 10 colonies are individually reanalysed, and all positive cases are serotyped to confirm the presence of O157 and H7.	Yes, standard methods	Information taken from a PhD thesis (2015) and not from a "real" laboratory protocol, which was confusing.

EC-48	M	Food	D	Detection of STEC O157 and non O157, other diarrhoeagenic E.coli, ST131, and ESBL producers	Mora et al, 2011b; Bustamant et al. 2011; Paton y Paton, 2002, 2005; Schmidt et al. 1995; Schultsz et al. 1994; Penteado et al. 2002	Food	25 g solid	Pre-enrichment, isolation, conventional PCR	<i>stx1</i> , <i>stx2</i> , <i>eae</i> , <i>eae-y1</i> , <i>wzx-O104</i> , <i>rfbO25b</i> (STEC); <i>aggR</i> , <i>aaiC</i> , <i>pCDV432</i> (EAEC); <i>eae</i> , <i>bfpA</i> (EPEC), ...		Enrichment of homogenized samples in BPW at 37°C, during 6h (B-1) and until 18-24h (B-2). After 6 h, isolation is attempted in: MACL, 37°C/18h (B-3) and MACL, 44°C/18h (B-5); MACSTC, 37°C/18h (B-4) and MACSTC, 44°C/18h (B-6), and in agar MACS, 37°C/18 h (A-2). PCR for, at least, <i>stx1</i> , <i>stx2</i> , <i>eae</i> , <i>bfpA</i> , <i>blaCTX-M</i> , <i>blaSHV</i> , and <i>rfbO25b</i> genes, using DNA extracted (boiling) from B-3, B-4, B-5, and B-6. In positive cases (for at least one gene), 50 colonies are reanalysed in groups of 10 colonies and after individually. Serotyping is performed in all positive cases. DNA isolated (boiling) from cultures at 37°C during 18-24h (B-2) is subject to PCR for STEC/EAEC/EPEC.	Yes, standard methods	Information taken from a PhD thesis (2015) and not from a "real" laboratory protocol, which was confusing.
EC-49	M	Food	T	Serotyping – Determination of O- and H-antigens	Guinée et al. 1981	<i>E. coli</i> isolates	Single colony	Serotyping	O- and H-antigens		Protocol described by Guinée et al. (1981). O-antigen detected by microagglutination and iH-antigen detected by agglutination in tube.	Yes, standard methods	Information taken from a PhD thesis (2015) and not from a "real" laboratory protocol, which was confusing. Fastidious method. Commercial antisera already available.
EC-50	M	Food	D	Genotyping by PCR	Mora et al. 2011, Schmidt et al. 1995, Brunder et al. 1999, Paton y Paton, 2005, Funk et al. 2013 Johnson et al. 1997, Yamamoto et al., 1995	<i>E. coli</i> isolates	7 µl extracted DNA	Conventional PCR	<i>stx1</i> , <i>stx2</i> , <i>eae</i> , <i>E-hlyA</i> , <i>katP</i> , <i>espP</i> , <i>subAB</i> , <i>iutA</i> , <i>iucD</i> (for O157:H7/HNM).		DNA template extracted by boiling. In food samples, DNA is extracted from 1/6 of a TSA confluent culture diluted in 300 µl of H ₂ O, and in pure strains from 1-2 colonies. PCR mix includes 0.2-0.5 µM of specific primers específicos, 6 µl of buffer (5X My Taq Red Reaction Buffer, Bioline), 1.5 mM MgCl ₂ , 50 mM ClK. 1u Taq (MyTaq™ DNA polymerase, Bioline), and H ₂ O until 30 ml. Amplification conditions: 94°C for 3 min, 35 cycles of 94°C for 1 min, annealing for 1 min 45 s, 72°C for 2	Yes, standard methods	Information taken from 2 PhD thesis (2016, 2018) and not from a "real" laboratory protocol, which was confusing.

											min, and finally 72°C for 3 min. Amplicons were analysed by electrophoresis (2% agarose in TBE).		
EC-51	M	Food	D/T	Detection and typing of verotoxins	Scheutz et al. 2012	<i>E. coli</i> isolates	5 µl extracted DNA	Conventional PCR	<i>stx1</i> , <i>stx2</i> , <i>stx1a</i> , <i>stx1c</i> , <i>stx1d</i> , <i>stx2a</i> , <i>stx2b</i> , <i>stx2c</i> , <i>stx2d</i> , <i>stx2e</i> , <i>stx2f</i> , <i>stx2g</i>		Protocol presented by Scheutz et al. 2012. PCR in a final volume of 20µ, and using HotStarTaq Master Mix (Qiagen).	Yes, standard methods	Information taken from 2 PhD thesis (2016, 2018) and not from a "real" laboratory protocol, which was confusing.
EC-52	M	Food	T	Typing of intimins	Blanco et al. 2004, 2006a, 2006b	<i>E. coli</i> isolates	5 µl extracted DNA	Conventional PCR	26 <i>eae</i> genes		Protocol developed and presented at Blanco et al. 2006 a, b	Yes, standard methods	Information taken from 2 PhD thesis (2016, 2018) and not from a "real" laboratory protocol, which was confusing.

EC-53	M	Food	T	Molecular typing by PFGE	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/it/supporting-publication/en-704	STEC strains	STEC strain	Molecular biology - Pulsed Field Gel Electrophoresis (PFGE), molecular typing method based on the restriction of the bacterial genome with rare cutting enzyme to generate pulsotypes	Bacterial genome	-	Protocol described at the reference (EFSA protocol)	The laboratory must have specific instruments for Pulsed field electrophoresis	Information taken from 2 PhD theses (2016, 2018) and not from a "real" laboratory protocol, which was confusing.
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Annex 2. Evaluation table of the protocols for the determination of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* AMR

Protocol ID	Institute ID	PH/Vet/ Food	Target (<i>Salmonella</i> or <i>Campylobacter</i>)	Title	Method	Inoculum	Growth medium incl. manufacturer	Incubation time	Incubation temp.	QC strains	Included antibiotics and concentrations	Manufacturer of plates, disks or strips	Interpretation	Comments
AMR-S-4	A	Vet	<i>Salmonella</i>	-	Broth microdilution, broth culture	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml (2x10 ⁵ -8x10 ⁵ CFU/ml)	CAMHB (Difco)	16-18 h	35°C	E.coli 2012-70-100-69 (EURL-AR)	According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	According to (2013/652/EU)	
AMR-S-3	G	PH/Vet	<i>Salmonella</i>	MIC determination of <i>Salmonella</i>	Broth microdilution (Trek-sensitire)	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	MH	18 ± 2 h	36-37	E.coli ATCC 25922	Following the harmonised EU method, ECDC	Sensititre	ECOFF or clinical acc to EUCAST or CLSI	Following the harmonised EU method, ECDC, WGS is used routinely
AMR-S-8	H	PH/Vet/Food	<i>Salmonella</i>								ampicillin, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, ceftazidime, ceftazidime, meropenem, pefloxacin, nalidixic acid, gentamicin, sulfisoxazole, trimethoprim, chloramphenicol, tetracycline, streptomycin, amoxicillin+clavulanic acid			Follows ECDC guideline. Colistin is tested with broth microdilution. If cefotaxim or ceftazidime resistance is detected double disk appr. synergy is performed. PCR for confirmation of ESBL and mcr-genes. If meropenem resistance is detected a ROSCO kit is used for confirmation of ESBLCARBA.
AMR-S-6	O	PH	<i>Salmonella</i>		Disk diffusion??						ampicillin (if R ertapenem, cefpodoxime, ceftazidime, ceftazidime, ceftazidime, trim/sulfa, pefloxacin, ceftriaxone,			

AMR-S-1	S	Vet	<i>Salmonella</i>		Broth microdilution						According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	According to (2013/652/EU)	Follows the recommendations of the EURL-AR entirely
AMR-S-2	T	Vet	<i>Salmonella</i>		Broth microdilution, colony suspension	1x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	CAMHBT (Sensititre)	18-20 h	35 ± 1°C		According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	According to (2013/652/EU)	
AMR-S-5	U	Vet	<i>Salmonella</i>	00-14-0280	Broth microdilution, colony suspension	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	CAMHB (MCS Diagnostics)	18-24 h	35°C		According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	According to (2013/652/EU)	
AMR-S-7	V	PH	<i>Salmonella</i>	KJ 9.15 M2	Broth microdilution, colony suspension	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml (2x10 ⁵ -8x10 ⁵ CFU/ml)	CAMHBT (Sensititre)	16-20 h	35°C	E.coli ATCC 25922		Sensititre		PCR kit for AMR in <i>Salmonella</i> Allplex Entero-RD Assay, Cat. No. CR9700Y, Seegene
AMR-S-9	W	PH	<i>Salmonella</i>		Disk diffusion		MHA (?)				ampicillin, cefepime, ceftazidime, meropenem, pefloxacin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole	?		Follows ECDC guideline for Enterobacterales. If pefloxacin resistance is detected the MIC is determined (method not specified)
AMR-C-5	A	Vet	<i>Campylobacter</i>	-	Broth microdilution, colony suspension	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml (2x10 ⁵ -8x10 ⁵ CFU/ml)	CAMHB (Difco) with 3% LHB	48 h	37°C	C. jejuni ATCC 33560	According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	According to (2013/652/EU)	
AMR-C-4	G	PH/Vet	<i>Campylobacter</i>	MIC determination of <i>Campylobacter</i>	Broth microdilution (Trek-sensitire)	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	MH + defib horse blood	Adequate, typically overnight	41,5°C	C. jejuni ATCC 33560	Following the harmonised EU method, ECDC	Sensititre	ECOFF or clinical acc to EUCAST or CLSI	Following the harmonised EU method, ECDC, WGS is used routinely
AMR-C-9	H	PH/Vet/Food	<i>Campylobacter</i>	Antimicrobial determinant protocol	Disk diffusion						ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, tetracycline			Follows ECDC guideline for <i>Campylobacter</i> .
AMR-C-7	O	PH	<i>Campylobacter</i>											
AMR-C-1	P	Vet/Food	<i>Campylobacter</i>		Broth microdilution,	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	MH + 2,5-5% LHB	24 ± 2 h	41 ± 1 °C	C. jejuni	According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	According to (2013/652/EU)	

					colony suspension					ATCC 33560			
AMR-C-2	S	Vet	<i>Campylobacter</i>		Broth microdilution, colony suspension						According to (2013/652/EU)		Follows the recommendations of the EURL-AR entirely
AMR-C-3	T	Vet	<i>Campylobacter</i>		Broth microdilution, colony suspension	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	CAMHBT with LHB (Sensititre) CP114-10	48 h	36 ± 1 °C		According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	alternative incubation 42°C for 24 h
AMR-C-6	U	Vet	<i>Campylobacter</i>	00-14-0280	Broth microdilution, colony suspension	5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	CAMHB with LHB (MCS Diagnostics)	48 h	36°C	C. jejuni ATCC 33560	According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	
AMR-C-8	V	PH	<i>Campylobacter</i>	KJ 9.15 M2	Broth microdilution, colony suspension	1,5-3x10 ⁶ CFU/ml	CAMHBT with LHB (Sensititre) CP112	24-48 h	41 ± 1 °C	C. jejuni ATCC 33560	According to (2013/652/EU)	Sensititre	
AMR-C-10	W	PH	<i>Campylobacter</i>		Disk diffusion		MHA (?) with 5% LHB				ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, tetracycline	?	Follows ECDC guideline for <i>Campylobacter</i> . If erythromycin resistance is suspected the MIC will be determined (method not specified)

Abbreviation	Whole name
CAMHB	Cation adjusted Mueller Hinton Broth
LHB	Lysed Horse Blood
MHA	Mueller Hinton Agar

Annex 3. Evaluation table of the protocols for the detection and characterisation of *Cryptosporidium* spp.

Protocol ID	Institute ID	PH/Vet/Food	Type of protocol (purification-enrichment/detection/typing)	Title	Reference	Panel detection or typing?	Matrix	Amount starting material	Principle of the method	Short description of the Procedure (equipment or other specific reagents needed)	Quantification possible?	Target(s) for species determination	Target(s) for subtyping	Comments on target(s)	Comments on to applicability in other labs	Additional comments
CR-P-1	A	Vet	purification-enrichment	Purification of <i>Giardia/Cryptosporidium</i>		N/A	feces	1 gram	Purification via sieving and flotation using glucose/saturated salt	1g feces is processed via sieving flotation and several washes. The end product is purified oocysts in 2 ml water.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes, standard protocol	Additional choline treatment possible but not used regularly. Quantification possible, each oocyst represents 200 OPG
CR-D-1	A	Vet	detection	Detection FITC		No	purified oocysts, feces, environmental samples (sludge)	1 gram feces via purification. Purified oocysts in 1 ml water	(FITC)-labelled monoclonal anti- <i>Cryptosporidium</i> antibodies are used to stain, fluorescence microscope is used for detection.	For purified oocysts: 10µl of homogenized sample is placed on well on slide. The sample is dried and fixated. (FITC)-labelled monoclonal anti- <i>Cryptosporidium</i> antibodies AquaGlo are used and after incubation the well is washed before addition of mounting fluid and cover glass. A fluorescence microscope is used for detection. The full well is counted. Each oocyst represents 200 OPG	Yes	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes, standard protocol	Possible to detect <i>Giardia</i> cysts as well
CR-T-1	A	Vet	typing	Typing or subtyping of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> sp.		No	purified oocysts or stool	N/A	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> species determination by nested PCR and	The molecular species determination of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. is performed on the basis of 18S SSU rRNA gene	N/A	18S (some times also 28S)	gp60 (Alves 2003) For some <i>Cryptosporidium</i> species other	For some <i>Cryptosporidium</i> species other	Yes, standard protocols	In some samples where amplification with Xiao primers are difficult we use Silva primer or 28S as described by Koehler et al

									Sanger sequencing. <i>Cryptosporidium</i> subtyping by nested PCR and Sanger sequencing.	amplification and sequencing using the primers described by Xiao et al. 1999. DNA extraction is performed with PowerLyser extraction kit according to Pettersson et al 2020. Amplification is performed using two µl of extracted DNA as template in the PCR (which is run with KAPA according to Åberg et al 2020). PCR products are analyzed on 1.5% agarose gel and positive products are sequenced using BigDye.			um species other primers are used	primers are used: Guo et al., 2015; Li et al., 2014; Rojas-Lopez et al., 2020; Stensvold et al., 2014; Stensvold et al., 2015b		
CR-D-2	F	PH	detection	Detection		Yes	Extracted DNA from human or animal	?	DNA extraction and real-time PCR	Three different DNA extraction methods are being used, automated DNA isolation on the MagNA Pure by Roche, QIAamp DNA minikit by Qiagen and the DNA stool kit by Qiagen.	Yes, relative quantification	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes, published protocol Verweij et al J. Clin. Microbiol. (2004)	
CR-T-2	F	PH	typing	Species determination			Extracted DNA	N/A	Real time PCR	Ordinary real time PCR and sanger sequencing equipment	N/A	Duplex real time PCR of AF190 627 (Hadfield et al. J. Clin. Microbiol. (2001)	gp60 by Peng et al. J. Eukaryot. Microbiol. (2001)	As an alternative also PCR primers that amplify a smaller gp60 fragment. The	Yes, standard protocols	

											ol. (2011) and gp60 (Roelf sema et al. Parasi t. Vector s (2016) .		amplifi cation proced ure also consist s of a nested PCR. The nested primers are a mixture of two forward primers and three reverse primers by Chalm ers et al. Parasit ol. (2017). For the first round we design ed primers that have not yet appear ed in a publica tion.	
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CR-P-2	G	PH/Vet	purification-enrichment	Microscopy of stool concentrates stained with Ziehl-Neelsen stain		N/A	Faeces		Concentration of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts in faecal samples by sieving and centrifugation	The faecal sample is mixed with 10% formalin solution, vortexed, and filtered through gauze. PBS is added, and the solution is centrifuged. The supernatant is discarded. 3 mL ethyl acetate and 7 mL formalin solution are added and the sample is subject to vortexing and centrifugation. Sediements are subject to acid-fast staining (Ziehl-Neelsen).	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		Flotation methods used for veterinary samples. Not usable for molecular methods since use of formalin??
CR-D-3	G	PH/Vet	detection	Microscopy of stool concentrates stained with Ziehl-Neelsen stain		Yes	Faeces	No specified amount	Specific Ziehl-Neelsen staining (acid-fast) for <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts in faecal concentrates	Light microscopy using oil lens (x100)	Yes, relative quantification	N/A	N/A	N/A	The method is known and used in many laboratories, but it should be performed only by experienced staff	

CR-D-4	G	PH/Vet	detection	PCR for <i>Cryptosporidium</i> , which is implemented in two tests: R077 (<i>Giardia</i> and <i>Cryptosporidium</i>), and R070 (<i>Giardia</i> , <i>Cryptosporidium</i> , and Entamoeba histolytica and dispar)		Yes	Faeces, water	200 mg of faeces for DNA extraction for PCR; varying amount for microscopy (Ziehl-Neelsen); for water samples, there is no specific starting amount (we only do this ad hoc)	real-time PCR using TaqMan probes	DNA extracted automatically on EMAG® (BioMerieux) is subject to real-time PCR. The 25-µL real-time PCR reaction mixture consists of 0.2 µL IMMOLASE™ DNA Polymerase (Bioline), 5 µL 10X ImmoBuffer, 1.25 µL (1 µM) of the primers and 0.125 µL (0.075 µM) of the probe, and 5 µL of DNA eluate. The real-time PCR is carried out using an Applied Biosystems 7500 Fast Real-Time PCR Thermocycler (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with the following cycling conditions: initial denaturation at 95 °C for 10 min, followed by 50 cycles of 95 °C for 15 sec, and 60 °C for 60 sec. PCR products are analyzed using Sequence Detection Software v.2.3 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). A sample is considered positive if an exponential curve was observed with a Ct-value ≤ 42. Negative (water) and positive controls (DNA for C. parvum) are included in each	Yes, relative quantification	N/A	N/A	N/A	The method is standardizable. Has been used on samples from humans and animals.	Modified from the original assay developed by Verweij et al. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC356880/
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										run as well as inhibition controls.					
CR-T-3	G	PH/Vet	typing	GP60 typing of <i>Cryptosporidium</i>		No	Genomic DNA from faecal samples	N/A	Nested PCR followed by Sanger sequencing	Species determination of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> is performed on the basis of 18S SSU rRNA gene amplification and sequencing using the primers described by Xiao et al. 1999. For gp60-based subtyping of e.g. <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>C. hominis</i> (which accounts for about 99% of our samples), we use the protocol by Alves et al. (2003). In case of <i>C. meleagridis</i> , we use the protocol described by Stensvold et al. (https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24740082/), and in case of <i>C. viatorum</i> , we use the protocol described by Stensvold et al. (https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25832304/). We are currently trying to	N/A	SSU rRNA gene (18S)	GP60	GP60 has been working best in our lab, but a major predicament is the fact that there is no fixed set of primers targeting all species. Hence, specific primers are needed, depending on species involved. We have	The method has been used for samples from humans and animals.

										work out a protocol for <i>C. suis</i> .				tried COWP with some successes. Meanwhile, hsp70-based typing has not worked well at all.		
CR-P-3	H	PH/Vet/Food	purification-enrichment	faeces concentration	https://eurlp.iss.it/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/MI-06-rev-3.pdf	N/A	Faeces		concentration and washing by centrifugation		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		Horton et al. 2018 Towards enhanced automated elution systems for waterborne protozoa using megazonic energy. J Microbiol. Meth. 145, 28-36
CR-D-5	H	PH/Vet/Food	detection	MI-06 IDENTIFICATION AT THE SPECIES LEVEL OF OOCYSTS OF <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. BY PCR/RFLP		No	Faeces, water, fruit and vegetable	1.0 mL of fecal sample containing 50% ethanol	microscopy after direct IF (Merifluor commercial kit by Meridian); nested-PCR; nested-PCR	Microscopy after direct IF (Merifluor commercial kit by Meridian); nested-PCR. DNA extraction, PCR and visualisation are described step by step in https://eurlp.iss.it/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/MI-06-rev-3.pdf	Yes, relative quantification	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes, protocol available.	The MI-06 method has been characterized in terms of sensitivity, specificity and repeatability. The results of the validation process confirmed that the method is suitable for the specified aim, and were evaluated by the Italian accreditation body (ACCREDIA) to accredit

										Reagents commercially available (some specified, e.g., QIAamp Fast DNA Stool, QIAGEN).						it according to the ISO/IEC 17025.
CR-T-4	H	PH/Vet/Food	typing	MI-06 IDENTIFICATION AT THE SPECIES LEVEL OF OOCYSTS OF <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. BY PCR/RFLP		No	Faeces	N/A	RFLP following nested PCR	A commonly employed method for molecular diagnostics of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> parasites is based on the amplification of a fragment of the gene encoding for a structural protein of the oocyst wall (<i>Cryptosporidium</i> Oocyst Wall Prorein, COWP). The sensitivity of the method has been established, and a nested PCR assay can detect the parasite in fecal samples containing <500 oocysts per gram (Pedraza-Diaz et al., 2001). The oligonucleotide pairs used for the two consecutive PCR reactions and the following enzymatic digestion of the amplification product permit to identify <i>Cryptosporidium</i> at specie level (Pedraza-Diaz et al., 2001 and Spano et al., 1997). By using PCR/RFLP, it is possible, based on the restriction patterns generated by the enzyme Rsa I,	N/A	COWP	NA		Standard protocol. Can be used for samples from humans and animals.	Typing method applicable to <i>C. parvum</i> , <i>C. hominis</i> , <i>C. canis</i> , <i>C. felis</i> , <i>C. meleagridis</i> , <i>C. andersoni</i> , <i>C. suis</i> , <i>C. ubiquitum</i> , Horse genotype - https://eur1p.iss.it/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/MI-06-rev-3.pdf The MI-06 method has been characterized in terms of sensitivity, specificity and repeatability. The results of the validation process confirmed that the method is suitable for the specified aim, and were evaluated by the Italian accreditation body (ACCREDIA) to accredit it according to the ISO/IEC 17025.

										<p>to distinguish the species <i>C. parvum</i>, <i>C. hominis</i>, <i>C. canis</i>, <i>C. felis</i>, <i>C. meleagridis</i>, <i>C. andersoni</i>, and the horse genotype. Since <i>C. suis</i> and <i>C. ubiquitum</i> have an identical Rsa I restriction pattern, their identification requires another restriction analysis using the enzyme Alu I. The method can be applied to fecal samples of human or animal origin, previously diagnosed as positive for the presence of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. Oocysts Method: MI-06 (described at https://eurtp.iss.it/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/MI-06-rev-3.pdf)</p>						
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CR-P-4	J	PH	purification-enrichment	feces parasites - eggs and cysts	<p>1. Ritchie L S. An ether sedimentation technique for routine stool examination. Bull U S Army Med Dep 1948;8:326.</p> <p>2. Allen A V H, Ridley D D. Further observations on the formol-ether concentration technique for faecal parasites. J Clin Path 1970;23:545-46.</p> <p>3. WHO 1994. Faecal concentration procedure - formalin - ether/ethyl acetate/gasoline. Bench Aids for the Diagnosis of Intestinal Parasites. Plate 2.</p> <p>4. Young K H, Bullock S L, Melvin D M, Sprull C L. Ethyl acetate as a substitute for diethyl ether in the Formalin-ether</p>	N/A	Feces	1 gram	Ethylacetat concentration by centrifugation	Fecal material is mixed with ethylacetat and then centrifuged which generates 4 layers with the oocysts in the bottom sediment.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes, standard in human diagnostic parasitology laboratories. However only used for microscopic methods. Not appropriate for molecular methods.	
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CR-D-6	J	PH	detection	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> , Cyclospora, Cystoisospora - Ziehl-Neelsen staining		No	concentrated feces	20 µl concentrated fecal material (start 1 g feces)	Acid fast oocysts are stained with charcoalfuchsin and background with malakitgreen and visualised in a light microscope	Material are first dried and fixated in methanol prior to staining with charcoalfuchsin.	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes, standards protocol and only needed is a light microscope. However, several of the reagents are hazardous. Nowadays many clinical diagnostic laboratories have turned to multiplex gastrointestinal PCR panels for detection.	Detects Cyclospora and Cystoisospora as well.
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CR-T-5	J	PH	typing	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> characterization and subtyping of species		No	Extracted DNA direct from feces	N/A	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> species determination by nested PCR and Sanger sequencing. <i>Cryptosporidium</i> subtyping by nested PCR and Sanger sequencing.	The molecular species determination of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. is performed on the basis of 18S SSU rRNA gene amplification and sequencing using the primers described by Xiao et al. 1999. DNA extraction is performed using the magLEAD 12gC instrument supplied with magDEA DX MV reagents (Precision System Science Co Ltd., Chiba, Japan). Amplification is performed using 1 and 2 µl of extracted DNA as template in the PCR. PCR products are analyzed on 1.5% agarose gel and positive products are sequenced using BigDye.	N/A	18S	gp60 (Alves 2003)	additionally primers used for other species: Guo et al., 2015; Li et al., 2014; Rojas-Lopez et al., 2020; Stensvold et al., 2014; Stensvold et al., 2015b	Yes, standard protocols	We run gp60 subtyping primarily and 18S on all negative samples. For species that is not amplified by Alvez gp60 primers we use the primers of that species.
CR-P-5	N	Vet	purification-enrichment	Detection of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> parasites in faecal samples by PCR	Stojceki K, Sroka J, Karamon J, Kusyk P, Cenczek T. Influence of selected stool concentration techniques on the effectiveness of PCR examination in <i>Giardia intestinalis</i>	N/A	stool	1 gram	Concentration of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts in faecal samples by sieving and centrifugation with a Percoll step	Method of centrifugal flotation with Percoll step. One gram of feces is mixed with 8 ml 25% Percoll solution and filtered through a plastic sieve into a beaker. The suspension is poured into a 15 ml conical centrifuge tube, followed by centrifugation at 1600 g for 5 min. Three volumes of	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	This method as simply, cheap and effective, can be used in many laboratories.	

					<p>diagnostics. Pol J Vet Sci. 2014, 17, 19-25.</p> <p>Karamon J, Ziomko I, Cencek T, Sroka J (2008)</p> <p>Modified flotation method with the use of Percoll for the detection of Isospora suis oocysts in suckling piglet faeces. Vet Parasitol 156: 324-328</p>					<p>saturated NaNO₃ are added to the sediment and mixed, followed by centrifugation at 1000 g for 10 min; 200 µl from top of the solution is then removed, place in a new 15-ml conical centrifuge tube and washed by centrifugation (1100g x 10 min) in 13 ml redistilled water. The sediment is stored at 4°C until further analysis.</p>					
CR-D-7	N	Vet	detection	<p>Detection of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> and <i>Giardia</i> parasites with the use of immunomagnetic separation and direct fluorescence assay</p>		water / wastewater		<p>Microscopy detection of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts and <i>Giardia</i> cysts in water/wastewater samples</p>	<p>Direct Immunofluorescence Assay (DFA). DFA is performed using commercial test Aqua-Glo™ G/C Direct Comprehensive Kit (Waterborne Inc., USA). Fifteen microliters of IMS product are put on microscopic slide and allowed to dry at room temperature. Next, samples are fixed by 50 µl of methanol and allowed to dry. After that, 50 µl of 4'-diamidino-2-phenyl indole (DAPI) in PBS (0.4 µg DAPI/ml) is dropped and left for 4 min at room</p>	N/A	N/A	N/A	<p>The method is known and used in many laboratories, but it can be performed by experienced staff</p>		

									<p>temperature. After removing DAPI, the slides are rinsed by adding 100 µl wash buffer and left for 1 minute. Then, the wash buffer is removed, and 50 µl of conjugate anti-<i>Cryptosporidium</i> /<i>Giardia</i> with fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) is placed in each well. The slides are placed in a humidified chamber and incubated at 37°C for 30 min. Then, a washing step is performed (as above described). A one drop of BlockOut™ counterstain (to reduce non-specific background fluorescence) is added to each well and slide is incubated for 1 minute at room temperature. After washing (as above described) and drying the slide, a drop of Fade™ mounting medium is placed in each well, covered by glass, and viewed under epifluorescence microscope (x 400). <i>Cryptosporidium</i> and <i>Giardia</i> (oo)cysts are identified on the basis of their size, shape, and structure</p>					
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										according to guideline described in method 1623. Positive and negative controls are used.					
CR-D-8	N	Vet	detection	Detection and species identification of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> parasites			Water, wastewater and faecal samples	N/A	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> DNA detection and <i>Cryptosporidium</i> species identification by RFLP and/or sequencing	The molecular identification of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. is performed on the basis of 18S SSU rRNA gene analysis using the primers described by Xiao et al. (2004) in modification by Santin et al. (2004). Negative and positive DNA control are included in each of PCR reactions. Amplification is performed using a TProfessional 48 thermal cycler (Biometra GmbH, Göttingen, Germany). After conducting the electrophoresis, PCR products are analyzed on 1.5% agarose gel stained	N/A	18S SSU rRNA (nested PCR), COWP (Real-time PCR)	N/a		These methods can be performed in other laboratories and their adaptation is not difficult.

										with ethidium bromide under UV light. To species determine, the positive samples are analyzed by RFLP and/or sequencing . Real Time PCR is performed according to Guy and al. (2003) with some modifications: the commercial mix IQ Supermix (Bio-Rad) is used and number of cycles is increased to 50. Real Time PCR is performed in a CFX96 Bio-Rad thermocycler.						
CR-P-6	O	PH	purification-enrichment	NA	NA	N/A	Feces	NA	Concentration of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts in faecal samples	NA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	NA	NA
CR-D-9	O	PH	detection	(MeriFluor <i>Cryptosporidium</i> /Giardia)		No	NA	NA	Immunofluorescence	Diagnosed by Direct Immunofluorescence method (MeriFluor <i>Cryptosporidium</i> /Giardia) following concentration of the fecal sample with formol-acetate.		N/A	N/A	N/A		After the imminent adaptation of the EntericBio system <i>Cryptosporidium</i> (along with Giardia and Entamoeba histolytica) will be diagnosed by PCR
CR-T-6	O	PH	typing	NA		No	NA	N/A	NA	NA	N/A	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

CR-P-7	P	Vet/Food	purification-enrichment	IMS purification	EURL Parasites (ISS Rome)	N/A	Feces		purification via Immunomagnetic separation		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	yes, transferred from EURL	
CR-D-10	P	Vet/Food	detection	Detection by nested PCR	Xiao et al. 1999 Genetic Diversity within <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i> and Related <i>Cryptosporidium</i> Species		purified oocysts, feces		nested PCR on 18s rRNA	DNA extraction with Qiamp DNA stool minikit (Qiagen) Nested PCR on 18s rRNA		N/A	N/A	N/A	yes, published protocol	
CR-T-7	P	Vet/Food	typing	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> species identification	feng et al. 2007 : Wide geographic distribution of <i>Cryptosporidium bovis</i> and the deer-like genotype in bovines		Feces	N/A	PCR-RFLP with SspI and MbolI enzymes on nested PCR products	RFLP is conducted on PCR products obtained for the detection part, with one or two enzymes (SspI, VspI, MbolI)	N/A	18s rRNA				
CR-T-8	P	Vet/Food	typing	C. parvum subtyping	Gatei et al. 2006 : Multilocus sequence typing and genetic structure of <i>Cryptosporidium hominis</i> from children in Kolkata, India Alves et al. 2003 : Subgenotyp		Feces	N/A	Sanger sequencing of GP60 with nested PCR products	DNA extraction as described for detection Nested PCR with AL3531 and AL353 primers then AL3532 and AL3534 primers Sanger sequencing on secondary PCR products with same primers use of the recommended nomenclature system for names of	N/A	GP60 (60 kda glycoprotein locus)				

					e Analysis of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> Isolates from Humans, Cattle, and Zoo Ruminants in Portugal					subtypes (Sulaiman et al. 2005, Xiao et al 2010)						
CR-P-8	Q	Vet	purification-enrichment	Detection and Enumeration of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> in Water by filtration, immunomagnetic separation and fluorescent antibody identification	USEPA Method 1622: <i>Cryptosporidium</i> in Water by Filtration/IMS/FA first published in 1999 and revised and updated in December 2005. The microbiology of Drinking Water (2009) (UK) – Part 14- Methods for the isolation, identification and enumeration of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts and <i>Giardia</i> cysts	N/A	Drinking water	Not applicable (this method is for detection of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts after filtration with IDEXX filtermaxpress filters)	Elution of oocysts from filters followed by IMS; Identification and quantification using 3 confirmative microscopic techniques: FITC staining, DAPI staining and differential interference contrast microscopy (DIC).	1. Sample elution from filters; 2. Centrifugation of eluent in the 500 mL centrifuge tubes at 2000 X G for 15 min. 3. Immunomagnetic separation of oocysts from pellet (using Dynabead anti- <i>Cryptosporidium</i> kit); 4. Sample staining with DAPI and Easy stain kit (BTF Australia); 5. Microscopic examination using an Epifluorescence microscope;	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	It's a laboratory method;	

CR-D-11	Q	Vet	detection	Detection and Enumeration of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> in treated water by filtration, immunomagnetic separation and fluorescent antibody identification		No	Filters (after water filtration)	Filters (after water filtration)	Elution of oocysts from filters followed by IMS; Identification and quantification using 3 confirmative microscopic techniques: FITC staining, DAPI staining and differential interference contrast microscopy (DIC).	1. Sample elution from filters; 2. Centrifugation of eluent in the 500 mL centrifuge tubes at 2000 X G for 15 min. 3. Immunomagnetic separation of oocysts from pellet (using Dynabead anti- <i>Cryptosporidium</i> kit); 4. Sample staining with DAPI and Easy stain kit (BTF Australia); 5. Microscopic examination using an Epifluorescence microscope;	Yes	N/A	N/A	N/A	Method is based on the USEPA Method 1622 and the UK method: The microbiology of Drinking Water (2009)	
CR-T-9	Q	Vet	typing	Method not applicable for typing		No		N/A			N/A					
CR-P-9	R	PH	purification-enrichment			N/A					N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		

CR-D-12	R	PH	detection				Faeces, sputum, BAL, etc, referred isolates, DNA?		Microscopy (including immunofluorescence) PCR-based tests		N/A	N/A	N/A		
CR-T-10	R	PH	typing				<i>Cryptosporidium</i> - positive stools (minimum 2 scoops, ideally without preservative), DNA (min 20µl) <i>Cryptosporidium</i> - positive water and testing slides	N/A		N/A					

Annex 4. Ranking Table for ETEC and STEC methods

1. Ranking scheme

Ranking/Scoring	High	Medium	Low	Unknown/Not applicable
For STEC methods: Detection of all STEC types	3 (Yes, all)	2 (all but one or a few STEC types)	1 (only a subset)	
For ETEC methods: Detection of both ST and LT	3 (Yes)		1 (No)	
Specificity	3	2	1	0
Sensitivity	3	2	1	0
Method recognised as	International standard or EURL method	National standard or NRL method or published method	internal method	0
Ease of implementation	3 (easy)	2 (Medium)	1 (difficult to implement)	
Equipment and facilities	3 (Typical, basic or common reagents and equipment)	2 (dedicated, Special equipment)	1 (Very sophisticated, difficult maintenance/calibration)	
Manhours	3 (Low, e.g. less than 3 hours)	2 (Medium, tentatively from 3 to 6 hours)	1 (Many, more than 6 hours)	
Analysis duration	3 (Short, besides incubation one day or less)	2 (Medium, besides incubation from 2 to 3 days)	1 (time consuming, more than 3 days)	
Sample collection and storage (including transport)	3 (Easy)	2 (Takes some time and particular attention to some aspects, including controlled temperature)	1 (Quite complicated, special equipment and training)	
Can the targets used in the method easily be changed, eg primers in a PCR assay, new microscope	3 (Yes, easily)	2 (takes some time)	1 (No)	
Number of critical control points	3 (A few)	2 (medium)	1 (Many)	
Complexity/preparation of sample	3 (very easy, the sample is used almost as such)	2 (needs some pre-processing)	1 (highly complex processing)	
Proficiency testing programs: Yes or no, not ranked				
Commercial kit	3 (commercial kit not used, besides sample treatment)	2 (Transparent)	1 (So, so)	0 (Black box)
Accredited method	3 Yes		1 No	0

Ease in results interpretation	3 (Easy or automated)	2 (medium)	1 (Quite complicated, special equipment and specific training)	
Comparability of results across the OH sector	3 Yes		1 No	
cost per sample	3 low	2 medium	1 high	
high throughput	3 easy	2 possible	1 not possible	
Reference material quoted in the protocol and well defined: Yes or no, nota ranked				

Requirements:

Define target(s) for

- ✓ STEC all STEC types positive for *Stx1* and/or *Stx2*. Consider including the *eae* gene and/or *aggR* gene.
- ✓ ETEC all ETEC types positive for ST and/or LT. Note: STa (STah, STap), STb1, STb2, e1l and eltIIabcde

Ranking of methods for STEC detection -1

Protocol ID	1	2	3	4	8	9	11	12	13		14		16
Institute ID	A	A	A	A	B	C	C	D	E		E		E
For STEC methods: Detection of all STEC types	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	3	1	O157, O26, O145, O111, O103 (Dyna), O55 (In-house)	0	Not specified which groups detected	3
Specificity (screening)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	According to literature; the sample matrix will impact the efficacy, DY beads for O111 work poorly - I suggest medium as O157, O26 and O55 are good	2		3
Sensitivity (screening)	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	2		3		3
Includes isolation attempt (Yes 3, No 1)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3		1		1
Method recognised as	1	1	1	1	3	1	3	2	2	Internal method? I suggest published method	2	I suggest at least published method	2
Ease of implementation	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2		3		2
Equipment and facilities	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	Magnetic beads and bead retriever	3		2

Manhours	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2		3		3
Analysis duration	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2		3		3
Can the targets used in the method easily be changed, eg primers in a PCR assay, new microscope	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2		1		3
Complexity/preparation of sample	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2		3		2
Proficiency testing programmes	Not for O103 alone	Not for O26 alone	Not for O121 alone	Probably for O157 alone	Yes	Yes	Yes	No?			Yes		Yes
Commercial kit	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	2	2		2		3
Accredited method	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	1	Only accreditation for O157	1		0
Ease in results interpretation	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	3	1		3		3
Comparability of results across the OH sector	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	1	Dependent on the sample matrix used (food difficult)	3		3
Cost per sample	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	3		3		2
High throughput	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1		1		3
Reference material quoted in the protocol and well defined	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No		No	In the kit	No
	38	38	38	36	42	38	40	43	29		37		41

Ranking of methods for STEC detection -2

Protocol ID	18	20		21		20&21	23	24	25	28	3	34&36 &39		37&38 &39		42		44		45		47	48	49
Institute ID	F	G		G		G	H	H	H	H	I	J		J		L		L		L		M	M	M
For STEC methods: Detection of all STEC types	3	2	Mixed culture more problematic, similar to G-21	2	Does not detect new stx2 subtypes (stx2h-2m) or new stx1 subtype (1e).	3	2	3	2	1	2	3		3		3	Difficult to evaluate. The information about the detection	3		3		2	3	3

				Should aaic/agg R be included? ?												on of vtx genes is not provid ed							
Specificity (screening)	0	N A		3		3	3	1	3	3	3	3		3		0	3	From the origin al paper s sensit ivity and sensi bility can be taken, and confri med by Angel a	3		0	0	0
Sensitivity (screening)	0	N A	Pure culture/is olate- high, mixed culture- lower	3		3	3	3	3	3	3	3		3		0	3		3		0	0	0
Includes isolation attempt (Yes 3, No 1)	1	3		3		3	3	1	1	3	3	3		3		1	Applie d to single colony	1	3	Only for the top 5 serogr oups	3	3	1
Method recognised as	1	2	NRL method	2		2	2	2	2	3	2	2		2		3	Difficul t to evalua te. The inform ation about the detecti on of	2	3	Same principl es and targets than the EU- protoc ol. Comm	2	2	2

																vtx genes is not provided					ertial kits			
Ease of implementation	2	2		2		2	2	1	2	2	2	2		2		3		3		2		3	3	2
Equipment and facilities	2	3		3		2	2	2	2	2	2	2		2		3		3		2		3	3	3
Manhours	3	2		2		3	2	2	1	2	2	2		1		2		2		2		1	1	1
Analysis duration	3	2		2		2	2	1	2	2	2	2		1		3		3		3		2	2	1
Can the targets used in the method easily be changed, eg primers in a PCR assay, new microscope	3	3	DEC PCR or stx subtyping PCR	3		3	3	1	2	3	3	3			NA?	1		2		1	Close commercial kits)	3	3	3
Complexity/preparation of sample	3	3	Isolation of STEC can be a bit complex	2	Cultivation, selection of colonies, lysis, centrifugation, dilution	3	2	2	2	2	2	2		2		3		3		2		2	2	3
Proficiency testing programs	Yes	No?		Yes		Yes, cultures	No	Yes (EQA-SSI)	No. Not specified in the method.	No	No	Yes (EQA-SSI)	Reference strains are analysed annually with assistance from ECDC	Yes	Not specified	Not specified	No	Not specified	No	Not specified	Yes	No	No	
Commercial kit	3	3		3		3	3	3	3	3	3	3		3		1		3		0		3	3	3
Accredited method	0	Yes	but not WGS	Yes?		3	3	1	1	1	0		No		No	3	Not specified	1	Not specified	3	Not specified	0	0	0
Ease in results interpretation	3	NA	Specific training - select colonies	2	Gel electrophoresis, unspecified	3	3	1	3	3	3	2	CT cut off values are not	2	Requires comparison	3		3		3		3	3	3

Ranking of methods for STEC characterisation

Protocol ID	10	17	19	26	27	29	30	35&36		43	50	51	52	53	22		
Institute ID	C	E	F	H	H	H	H	J		L	M	M	M	M	G		
For STEC methods: Detection/characterization of all STEC types: namely stx genes subtyping and detection of eae and aggR genes (3 stx subtyping or eae or aggR, 1 none of them)	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	1		3	3	2	2	Same than ISS_8 - Nadi a	3	Does not detect/type new stx2 subtypes (stx2h-2m) or new stx1 subtype (1e)- we want to stick on these subtypes	1
Specificity	3	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA		3	0	0	0		3		3
Sensitivity	3	NA	NA	NA	3	NA	NA	NA		3	0	0	0		3		3
Method recognised as	3	2	1	3	3	3	3	2		3	2	3	2		3	International standard or EURL method	2
Ease of implementation	3	2	1	2	2	2	1	1		2	3	3	3		2	Adjust to correct annealing temperature	3
Equipment and facilities	2	2	1	2	3	2	3	1		3	3	3	3		3		3
Manhours	3	3	3	2	2	2	1			2	2	2	2		2		2
Analysis duration	3	3	2	2	2	2	3	2		2	3	3	3		2		3
Can the targets used in the method easily be changed, eg primers in a PCR assay, new microscope	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3		3	3	3	3		3	Need detailed overview of all stx variants and careful implementation (annealing temp) to eliminate cross-reactions	2
Complexity/preparation of sample	3	3	3	2	2	2	1	2		2	3	3	3		2		3

Proficiency testing programs	Yes	Yes	The existing ones (for instance those from ECDC or EURL for E. coli or CARE) can be used	Not specified in the method. Commercial available for some of the serogroups. EURL PT.	Yes (EQA-SSI and EURL for E. coli)	Yes (EQA-SSI and EURL for E. coli)	No more available			No	Yes	Yes	No		Yes		No
Commercial kit	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	3		3	3	3	3		3	Need to use Qiagen HotStarTaq Master Mix Kit	3
Accredited method	3	0	0	1	1	3	3	3	No	3	0	0	0		0	It does not say in the protocol	3
Ease in results interpretation	2	3	3	2	1	3	2	2	CT cut off values are not specified. Might be specified in another unsubmitted protocol.	3	3	3	3		3	Gel electrophoresis, unspecific band pattern (annealing temp)	3
Comparability of results across the OH sector	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3		3	3	3	3		3		3
Cost per sample	2	2	1	2	2	3	2	2		2	3	3	3		3		3
High throughput	3	3	3	2	2	3	2	3		2	2	2	2		2	Change from gel electrophoresis is to capillary electrophoresis (need F-primer with fluorochrome)?	2
Reference material quoted in the protocol and well defined	Yes	Yes, but not well detailed	No	No	Yes	No		Yes		No	No	No	No		Yes		No
Final score	45	33	27	30	38	35	30	28		42	36	36	35	0	40		42
	only eae	serogroup	detection of	detection of	Detection of	detection of	PFGE typing	detection of serogroups		Detection of stx subtypes					Detection of stx subtypes		aggR

	from ISO/TS 13136	associated genes	serogroups	serogroups	stx subtypes	serogroups					
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Ranking of methods for ETEC detection

Protocol ID	5	31	46		41	20&21
Institute ID	A	H	L		L	G
For ETEC methods: Detection of both ST and LT	3	3	1		1	3
Specificity	3	3	0		3	3
Sensitivity	3	3	0		3	3
Includes isolation attempt (Yes 3, No 1)	1	3	3		3	3
Method recognised as	2	3	2		2	2
Ease of implementation	3	2	3		3	2
Equipment and facilities	3	2	3		3	2
Manhours	3	2	3		2	3
Analysis duration	3	2	2		3	2
Can the targets used in the method easily be changed, eg primers in a PCR assay, new microscope	0	3	3		2	3
Complexity/preparation of sample	3	2	2		3	3
Proficiency testing programs	no		No		No	Yes, cultures
Commercial kit	3	3	3		3	3
Accredited method	1	3	1	Not specified	3	3
Ease in results interpretation	0	3	3		3	3
Comparability of results across the OH sector	0	3	3		3	3
Cost per sample	3	2	3		3	3
High throughput	2	3	2		2	2
Reference material quoted in the protocol and well defined	No	No	No		No	Yes

	36	45	37		45	46

Ranking of methods for ETEC characterisation

Protocol ID	7	40	6	15
Institute ID	B	K	A	E
For ETEC methods: Detection of both ST and LT and ETEC colonization factors (3 toxins and CF, 1 only toxins)	1	1	3	3
Specificity	NA	NA	3	3
Sensitivity	NA	NA	3	3
Method recognised as	3	2	2	2
Ease of implementation	3	3	2	3
Equipment and facilities	2	3	2	3
Manhours	3	3	2	2
Analysis duration	3	3	2	3
Can the targets used in the method easily be changed, eg primers in a PCR assay, new microscope	3	3	2	3
Complexity/preparation of sample	3	3	3	3
Proficiency testing programs			Yes	Yes
Commercial kit	3	3	3	3
Accredited method	1	0	3	0
Ease in results interpretation	2	2	3	2
Comparability of results across the OH sector	3	NA	3	3
Cost per sample	2	3	2	3
High throughput	3	2	2	1
Reference material quoted in the protocol and well defined	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Final score	35	31	40	40

Annex 5 – Ranking table for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

Method	Disk diffusion and diffusion based MIC methods for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Salmonella</i> and thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i>		Dilution based MIC methods for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of <i>Salmonella</i> and thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i>	
	Score	Comment	Score	Comment
Specificity	0	Essential agreement with ISO (<i>Salmonella</i>) or CLSI (<i>Campylobacter</i>) method should be documented for the MIC based methods	0	Essential agreement with ISO (<i>Salmonella</i>) or CLSI (<i>Campylobacter</i>) method should be documented for the MIC based methods
Sensitivity	0	Essential agreement with ISO (<i>Salmonella</i>) or CLSI (<i>Campylobacter</i>) method should be documented for the MIC based methods	0	Essential agreement with ISO (<i>Salmonella</i>) or CLSI (<i>Campylobacter</i>) method should be documented for the MIC based methods
Method recognised as	3	International standard (ECDC approved)	3	International standard - ECDC, EFSA and EURL approved
Ease of implementation	3		2	
Equipment and facilities	3		1	In most cases proprietary methods are used - and there is a need for investment in equipment
Manhours	0	Depending on individual laboratory set up	0	Depending on individual laboratory set up
Analysis duration	0	From a pure culture - until result 16-24 hours	0	From a pure culture - until result 16-24 to 48 hours - depending in incubation temperature
Sample collection and storage (including transport)	0	Samples is a pure culture	0	Samples is a pure culture
Can the targets used in the method easily be changed, eg primers in a PCR assay, new microscope	3	Easy to test new antimicrobials, just change disks	1	Assay design often fixed by the supplier - and inflexible
Number of critical control points	1		2	
Complexity/preparation of sample	2	Can be tricky for <i>Campylobacter</i> due to swarming.	2	Pure cultures are essential for the performance of the method
Proficiency testing programmes	3		3	

Commercial kit	0	Use of commercial disks and strips recommended	1	In most cases proprietary methods are used - and there is a need for investment in equipment
Accredited method	2		2	
Ease in results interpretation	2		3	
Typing	0	Antimicrobial susceptibility is a phenotypic trait - and can be used as a typing method	0	Antimicrobial susceptibility is a phenotypic trait - and can be used as a typing method
Comparability of results across the OH sector	3	Broth dilution methods usually considered better than diffusion based, but diffusion based methods work well for most antimicrobials	3	
Cost per sample	0	Depending on individual laboratory set up, but in many cases cheaper than diffusion based MIC methods		Depending on individual laboratory set up
High throughput		Depending on individual laboratory set up	0	Depending on individual laboratory set up
Final score	25		23	

Annex 6 Procedure for the detection of ETEC and STEC in human samples

OH-Harmony-CAP: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR determinants

Procedure for the detection and isolation of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC) and Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) in human samples

1. Introduction

The present procedure represents the output of the work carried out in WP4 of the OH-EJP project OH-Harmony-Cap. In particular, in the activities of this WP, a ranking of procedures was carried out to propose a harmonised procedure for STEC and ETEC detection. This exercise has been done on the basis of protocols collected from several Institutes in the EU and UK operating in different areas, namely public health, veterinary and food sectors. A group of scientists with expertise on STEC and ETEC has been working to elaborate the ranking exercise, and the results can be found in the deliverable 4.1 of the project, consisting in a technical Report of the activities carried out in WP4 of the project. This report is available at this link ([link](#)).

The detection of STEC and ETEC in the veterinary sector is carried out according to the standard method ISO TS 13136:2012 and EURL for *E. coli* protocols. The present procedure aims at giving support to laboratories dealing with the diagnosis and confirmation of infections in humans, and consists of an adaptation of one protocol in use in a laboratory from a partner Institute of the OH-Harmony-Cap project, acknowledged at the end of this document.

2. Aim and field of application

Diarrhoeagenic *E. coli* are able to cause disease in humans, and are grouped based on the presence of certain virulence genes, particularly those encoding toxins (Nataro and Kaper, 1998). This procedure aims at detecting Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC) and Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), selected for the purposes of OH-Harmony-Cap, nonetheless the original procedure targeted also Enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC) and Enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC).

The present procedure is based on the detection by PCR amplification of *stx* coding genes for STEC detection and *eht* and *est* genes characteristic of ETEC.

The test samples to be included in the workflow of the present procedure may be different, including more likely faecal samples, and in special cases blood or urine specimens, mixed bacterial cultures or isolated *E. coli* strains and the protocol shall be applied to bacterial cultures grown onto a selective/differential solid medium appropriate for *Escherichia coli* (e.g. TBX or MacConkey plates). The bacterial cultures may represent either first isolation plates from complex clinical specimens, or mixed and pure bacterial cultures sent to the laboratory for confirmation. The aim of the method is to reveal the presence of the virulence genes targeted here in *E. coli* colonies, in order to isolate STEC and ETEC from a complex specimen. In case of confirmation, the objective is to determine the presence of the target virulence genes in *E. coli* isolates.

3. Normative references

- ISO 6887 (all parts), Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination
- ISO 7218, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — General requirements and guidance for microbiological examinations.
- ISO 11133, Microbiology of food, animal feed and water — Preparation, production, storage and performance testing of culture media
- ISO 22174, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — General requirements and definitions
- ISO 22118, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection and quantification of food-borne pathogens — Performance characteristics

4. Abbreviations

PCR: polymerase chain reaction
 MAC: MacConkey agar
 TBX: tryptone bile X-glucuronide agar
 STEC: Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli*
stx: Stx-coding gene
eht: heat labile toxin coding gene
est_h: gene encoding the heat stable enterotoxin A (human variant)
est_p: gene encoding the heat stable enterotoxin A (porcine variant)

5. Procedure for the PCR determination of *stx1*, *stx2* and genes coding for ST and LT

5.1 Template preparation

The primary plate is examined for various colony morphologies, and three single colonies with *E. coli* morphology are picked with a sterile 1 µl loop and suspended in 100 µl of nuclease-free water and boil for 10 minutes. The three colonies are tested for the presence of target virulence genes, and in case they result negative the process is continued to test up to 15 colonies.

Any method in use in the laboratory (e.g. chelex-based non immobilized resins) can also be applied for the purification of DNA from single colonies.

Please note that too much DNA (colony mass) will give non-specific bands.

Important: In case of testing complex samples, such as faecal samples, it might be useful to test the area of confluent growth from the primary plate too, particularly picked from two different areas of the plate, to have an indication that the sample may contain ETEC or STEC. Touch the area with the 1 µl loop and suspended in 100 µl of nuclease-free water and boil for 10 minutes and then proceed with the PCR determinations, together with the first batch of three isolated colonies.

5.2 Reaction mix

Set up a reaction mix according to the manufacturers recommendations of the polymerase used:

Reagent	Final Concentration
Reaction Buffer	1X
MgCl ₂	1.5 mM
dNTPs	0.2 mM
Primers	0.5 µM (each primer)
Taq polymerase	2.5 U

A ready-to-use master mix, containing the reaction buffer, MgCl₂, dNTPs and Taq Polymerase, can also be used, depending on its availability. Prepare a 25 µl mix by adding nuclease-free water and 5 µl of DNA template.

A negative control shall be used in all reactions, consisting of a reaction mixture added with 5 µl of nuclease-free water. Positive controls consisting of DNA prepared from reference strains shall be added at each working session (see the reference strains' section)

5.3 Primer pairs and thermal profiles

The primer sequences and the amplicon sizes expected for *eae* and *aggR* detection are reported in the table below.

Primer name	Target	Sequence (5'-3')	Amplicon size	Thermal profile	Reference
PS3	<i>stx1</i>	GTTTGCAGTTGATGTCAGAGGGA	260 bp	94°C 2 min – 35X: 94°C 50sec, 62 °C 40 sec, 72°C 50 sec – 72°C 3 min – 4°C ∞	Persson et al, 2007
PS15	<i>stx1d</i>	ATTTGCAGTCGATATCATGGGGT			
PS16		CARCGAATGGCGATTTATCTGC			
PS7	<i>stx2</i>	GCCTGTCGCCAGTTATCTGACA	254 bp	“	“
PS8		GGAATGCAAATCAGTCGTCCTACTC			

PS9	<i>eltf</i>	AAACCGGCTTTGTCAGATATGATG A	479 bp	“	“
PS10		TGTGCTCAGATTCTGGGTCTCCT			
StFh	<i>esta_h</i>	TTTCGCTCAGGATGCTAAACCAG	151 bp	“	“
StRh		CAGGATTACAACACAATTCACAGC AGTA			
StFp	<i>esta_p</i>	CTTTCCCCTCTTTTAGTCAGTCAA CTG	160 bp	“	“
StRp		ACAGAATCGTCAGCATCAGC			

Table 1. Primers and sequences

5.4 Agarose gel electrophoresis

Prepare a 1.5-2 % (w/v) agarose gel in 1X Tris/Borate/EDTA (TBE) or Tris/Acetate/EDTA (TAE). Each well of the gel is loaded with 15 µl of each reaction added with loading die at 1X final concentration. Run the samples in 1X running buffer (TBE or TAE) in constant voltage (100 V). Use a proper stain for visualizing on a UV transilluminator the DNA fragments in the gel after the run. A molecular weight marker suitable for assignment of the correct molecular weights to the amplicons produced (refer to table 1) shall be loaded.

5.5 Interpretation of the results

The correct band assignment is a crucial point in the assessment of the presence of the virulence genes. Samples showing amplification fragments of the expected size (See 5.4 and Annex 1) are considered as positive for related target genes. Make sure that the bands produced by the control strains match exactly the expected molecular weight, and that the negative controls are not showing any amplification products.

5.6 Reference strains

DNA template extracted from strains possessing the target genes shall be used in each analytical session.

Examples of reference strains available for this purpose are reported below:

C210-03: Shigatoxin producing *E. coli*, *eae+* *stx1+* *stx2+*

H10407: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *eltf+*, *esta_p+*, commercially available

EF451: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *eltf+*, *esta_p+*

EA22: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *esta_r+*

The reference strains to be used as positive controls can be requested at the EURL for *E. coli* (<https://www.iss.it/en/web/iss-en/coli-activities-and-services>) or at the International *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella* Centre, Department of Bacteria, Parasites and Fungi, at the Statens Serum Institut (fsc@ssi.dk).

5.7 Equipment needed

- Laminar flow hood
- Laminar flow hood for PCR
- Disposable bacteriology loops of 1 and 10 µl
- 15 µl snap cap tubes
- 500 ml flasks
- 500 ml and 1l cylinders
- Bacteriology plates
- Incubator (37 ± 1 ° C)
- Fridge-freezer
- Technical scale suitable for weighing in the 0.5-100 g range
- Automatic variable volume pipettes (P10, P20, P100, P200, P1000)
- Sterile tips with anti-aerosol filter
- 1.5 ml Eppendorf type tubes
- 0.2 ml tubes or 96-well PCR platelets with seal
- Heating plate or Thermoblock
- Rotating agitator
- Magnetic stir bar

- Thermal cycler (no particular specific requests are required)
- Horizontal electrophoresis apparatus
- U.V. transilluminator

5.8 Reagents

- Sterile deionized water free of contaminating nucleases
- Deoxyribonucleotides in 10 mM stock solution
- Synthetic oligonucleotides in solution (100 pmoles/ μ l in water)
- *Taq* DNA polymerase + reaction buffer
- Tris Acetate EDTA Buffer or Tris Borate EDTA buffer
- Loading buffer (purchased ready for use)
- Agarose gel (for molecular biology)
- Agarose gel stain (purchased ready for use)
- Nutrient agar (e.g. TSA)

Acknowledgments

OH-Harmony-Cap project would like to acknowledge the following laboratory for the support and allowing the proposal of harmonised procedures:

- The International Collaborating Centre for Reference and Research on *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella*, Staten Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark

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Nataro J.P., and J.B. Kaper. 1998. Diarrheagenic *Escherichia coli*. Clin Microbiol Rev. 11:142-201.
Persson, S., K. E. P. Olsen, F. Scheutz, K. A. Krogfelt, and P. Gerner-Smidt. 2007. A method for fast and simple detection of major diarrhoeagenic *Escherichia coli* in the routine diagnostic laboratory. Clinical Microbiol. Infect. 13:516-524.

Annex 7 Procedure for the characterisation of STEC

OH-Harmony-Cap: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR determinants

Procedure for the characterization of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC): detection of *eae* and *aggR* genes and determination of *stx* genes subtypes

1. Introduction

The present procedure represents the output of the work carried out in WP4 of the OH-EJP project OH-Harmony-Cap. In particular, in the activities of this WP, a ranking of procedures was carried out to propose a harmonised procedure for STEC characterization. This exercise has been done based on protocols collected from several Institutes in the EU and UK operating in different areas, namely public health, veterinary and food sectors. A group of scientists with expertise on STEC has been working to elaborate the ranking exercise, and the results can be found in the deliverable 4.1 of the project, consisting in a technical Report of the activities carried out in WP4 of the project. This report is available at this link ([link](#)).

The general criteria for the design of a harmonised procedure for STEC strains agreed by the experts is in line with the latest pathogenicity assessment issued by EFSA in 2020 [1], and concern the identification of *stx* genes subtypes and the determination of the colonization-associated genes *eae* and *aggR*. The present procedure consists in an adaptation of three protocols in use in different Institutes, acknowledged at the end of this document, who collaborated in the OH-Harmony-Cap WP4 collection.

2. Aim and field of application

Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC) are able to elaborate potent cytotoxins, the Stx. The Stx family is divided into two branches, Stx1 and Stx2, based on their antigenic differences. Several Stx1 and Stx2 subtypes have been described, and some of them are clinically relevant in that they are produced by strains isolated from cases of haemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) (Bielaszewska 2006, Persson 2007, Friedrich 2002), while others are primarily associated with milder course of disease (Persson 2007 and Friederich 2002).

Several STEC strains inducing disease in humans are able to colonize the human host through the characteristic intimate adhesion mechanism known as “attaching and effacing” (A/E), through the expression of genes located onto a pathogenicity island named LEE. The gene *eae* encodes the adhesion intimin, a key factor in the A/E colonization mechanism, and is considered a hallmark of the presence of the LEE.

Some *E. coli* strains may possess combination of pathogenic features typical of enteroaggregative *E. coli* together with the capacity to produce Shiga toxin (Scheutz et al 2011), representing pathogens of public health concern due to the severity of symptoms they are able to induce. Among other features, *aggR* gene is typical of enteroaggregative *Escherichia coli* (EAggEC) and can be used as a marker of the enteroaggregative colonization features.

The characterization of *stx*-genes subtypes and the presence of colonization-associated genes *eae* and *aggR* are considered pivotal for the pathogenicity assessment (EFSA 2020).

This procedure describes the detection of *Escherichia coli* virulence genes *eae*, encoding the adhesin intimin associated to the A/E phenotype, and *aggR*, involved in the enteroaggregative adhesion pattern. Moreover, indication on the procedure for the determination of *stx* genes subtyping is provided.

This protocol shall be applied to pure STEC cultures, isolated from any source, with any method, and is based on conventional PCR.

3. Normative references

- ISO 6887 (all parts), Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination
- ISO 7218, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — General requirements and guidance for microbiological examinations.

- ISO 11133, Microbiology of food, animal feed and water — Preparation, production, storage and performance testing of culture media
- ISO 22174, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — General requirements and definitions
- ISO 22118, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection and quantification of food-borne pathogens — Performance characteristics
- ISO 23418, Whole genome sequencing for typing and genomic characterization of foodborne bacteria — General requirements and guidance

4. Abbreviations

PCR: polymerase chain reaction

TSA: Tryptone Soy Agar

STEC: Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli*

eae: intimin-coding gene

aggR: gene encoding a transcriptional regulator of enteroaggregative *Escherichia coli*

stx: Stx-coding gene

5. Procedure for the PCR determination of *eae* and *aggR* genes

5.1 Template preparation

DNA can be purified from single colonies streaked onto solid agar plates, with any method in use in the laboratory (e.g. chelex-based non immobilized resins). Below the simple extraction by boiling method is described:

- ✓ Streak the pure STEC culture onto solid medium (e.g. TSA)
- ✓ Pick a single bacterial colony with a sterile 1 µl loop
- ✓ Suspend the colony in 100 µl of nuclease-free water and boil for 10 minutes.
- ✓ Use 5 µl as template in PCR reactions

Important: Too much DNA (colony mass) will give non-specific bands.

5.2 Reaction mix

Set up a reaction mix according to the manufacturers recommendations of the polymerase used:

Reagent	Final Concentration
Reaction Buffer	1x
MgCl ₂	1.5 mM
dNTPs	0.2 mM
Primers	0.5 µM (each primer)
Taq polymerase	2.5 U

A ready-to-use master mix, containing the reaction buffer, MgCl₂, dNTPs and *Taq* Polymerase, can also be used, depending on its availability. In this case, the amplification conditions, including the thermal profile, shall be adapted according to the manufacturers' instruction (e.g. hot start *Taq*). Prepare a 25 µl mix by adding nuclease-free water and 5 µl of DNA template. A negative control shall be used in all reactions, consisting of a reaction mixture added with 5 µl of nuclease-free water. Positive controls consisting of DNA prepared from reference strains shall be added at each working session (see the reference strains' section)

5.3 Primer pairs and thermal profiles

The primer sequences and the amplicon sizes expected for *eae* and *aggR* detection are reported in the table below. The PCRs shall be set up separately for the two targets, since the annealing temperatures are not overlapping

Target	Sequence (5'-3')	Amplicon size	Thermal profile	Reference
<i>eae</i>	GGYCAGCGTTTTTCCTTC CTG	377 bp	94°C 2 min – 35X: 94°C 50sec, 62°C 40 sec, 72°C 50 sec – 72°C 3 min – 4°C ∞	Persson et al, 2007
	TCGTCACCARAGGAATCG GAG			

aggR	GTATACACAAAAGAAGGA AGC	254 bp	94°C 5 min – 35X: 94°C 1 min, 56 °C 1 min, 72°C 2 min – 72°C 4 min – 4°C ∞	Fujioka M et al, 2013
	ACAGAATCGTCAGCATCA GC			

Table 1. Primers and sequences used for *ae* and *aggR* detection

5.4 Agarose gel electrophoresis

Prepare a 1.5-2 % (w/v) agarose gel in 1x Tris/Borate/EDTA (TBE) or Tris/Acetate/EDTA (TAE). Each well of the gel is loaded with 15 µl of each reaction added with loading dye at 1X final concentration. Run the samples in 1x running buffer (TBE or TAE) in constant voltage (100 V). Use a proper stain for visualizing on a UV transilluminator the DNA fragments in the gel after the run. A molecular weight marker suitable for assignment of the correct molecular weights to the amplicons produced (refer to table 1) shall be loaded.

5.5 Interpretation of the results

The correct band assignment is a crucial point in the assessment of the presence of the virulence genes. Samples showing amplification fragments of the expected size (See 5.4) are considered as positive for related target genes. Make sure that the bands produced by the control strains match exactly the expected molecular weight, and that the negative controls are not showing any amplification products.

5.6 Reference strains

DNA template extracted from strains possessing the target genes shall be used in each analytical session.

Examples of reference strains available for this purpose are reported below:

NCTC12900: Non toxigenic *E. coli*, commercially available, O157 *ae*+

CDC 3250-76: Enteroagregative *E coli*, O111 *aggR*+

EF129: Enteropathogenic *E. coli*, O45 *ae*+

C679-12: Enteroagregative *E. coli*, O104 *aggR*+

The reference strains to be used as positive controls can be requested at the EURL for *E. coli* (<https://www.iss.it/en/web/iss-en/coli-activities-and-services>) or at the International *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella* Centre, Department of Bacteria, Parasites and Fungi, at the Statens Serum Institut (fsc@ssi.dk).

5.7 Equipment needed

- Laminar flow hood
- Laminar flow hood for PCR
- Disposable bacteriology loops of 1 and 10 µl
- 15 ml snap cap tubes
- 500 ml flasks
- 500 ml and 1l cylinders
- Bacteriology plates
- Incubator (37 ± 1 ° C)
- Fridge-freezer
- Technical scale suitable for weighing in the 0.5-100 g range
- Automatic variable volume pipettes (P10, P20, P100, P200, P1000)
- Sterile tips with anti-aerosol filter
- 1.5 ml Eppendorf type tubes
- 0.2 ml tubes or 96-well PCR platelets with seal
- Heating plate or Thermoblock
- Rotating agitator
- Magnetic stir bar
- Thermal cycler (no particular specific requests are required)
- Horizontal electrophoresis apparatus
- U.V. transilluminator

5.8 Reagents

- Sterile deionized water free of contaminating nucleases

- Deoxyribonucleotides in 10 mM stock solution
- Synthetic oligonucleotides in solution (100 pmoles/μl in water)
- *Taq* DNA polymerase + reaction buffer
- Tris Acetate EDTA Buffer or Tris Borate EDTA buffer
- Loading buffer (purchased ready for use)
- Agarose gel (for molecular biology)
- Agarose gel stain (purchased ready for use)
- Nutrient agar (e.g. TSA)

6. Procedure for the identification of *stx1* and *stx2* genes subtypes

The selected protocol for the identification of three *stx1* and seven *stx2* genes subtypes (*stx1a*, *stx1c* and *stx1d*; *stx2a* to *stx2g*) is well detailed and available at the EURL for *E. coli* website as well as at the Statens Serum Institut website at the following links:

- ✓ https://www.iss.it/documents/5430402/0/EURL-VTEC_Method_06_Rev+2.pdf/20226358-3792-de68-2f24-1f0249466e0e?t=1619466269431
- ✓ <https://www.ssi.dk/-/media/arkiv/dk/sygdomme-beredskab-og-forskning/sygdomsovervaagning/referencelaboratorier/stx-detection--subtyping-protocolrev7.pdf?la=da>

Acknowledgments

OH-Harmony-Cap project would like to acknowledge the following laboratories for their support and willingness to participate in the project, and allowing the proposal of harmonised procedures:

- The International Collaborating Centre for Reference and Research on *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella*, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark
- Laboratório Nacional de Referência de Infecções Gastrointestinais, Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge, Lisbon, Portugal
- European Union Reference Laboratory for *E. coli*, Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Rome, Italy

References

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- Persson, S., K. E. P. Olsen, F. Scheutz, K. A. Krogfelt, and P. Gerner-Smidt. 2007. A method for fast and simple detection of major diarrhoeagenic *Escherichia coli* in the routine diagnostic laboratory. *Clinical Microbiol. Infect.* 13:516-524.

Annex 8 Method for the characterisation of ETEC

OH-Harmony-Cap: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR determinants

Procedure for the characterization of Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC): detection of heat labile and heat stable toxins coding genes as well as genes encoding a set of colonization factors

1. Introduction

The present procedure represents the output of the work carried out in WP4 of the OH-EJP project OH-Harmony-Cap. In particular, in the activities of this WP, a ranking of procedures was carried out to propose a harmonised procedure for STEC characterization. This exercise has been done on the basis of protocols collected from several Institutes in the EU and UK operating in different areas, namely public health, veterinary and food sectors. A group of scientists with expertise on pathogenic *E. coli* has been working to elaborate the ranking exercise, and the results can be found in the deliverable 4.1 of the project, consisting in a technical Report of the activities carried out in WP4 of the project. This report is available at this link ([link](#)).

The general criteria for the design of a harmonised procedure for the characterization of ETEC strains agreed by the experts concern the identification of the genes coding the major toxins elaborated by these strains, together with a panel of colonization factors coding genes. As a matter of fact, among the protocols collected only a few aimed at the detection of adhesins, and only in the veterinary area. Therefore, the present procedure indicates the detection of colonization factors described in the ETEC animal host, considering that they may also be overlooked in human cases of ETEC infections.

This procedure consists in an adaptation of protocols in use in different Institutes, acknowledged at the end of this document, partners of the OH-Harmony-Cap WP4.

2. Aim and field of application

Infection sustained by Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC) is the most common type of colibacillosis of young animals, and it is also a significant cause of food- and waterborne human diarrhea worldwide (Duan et al 2012). ETEC is a pathotype characterized by the production of adhesins that mediate bacterial adherence to the intestinal epithelium, also known as colonisation factors (CFs) and enterotoxins that interact with the intestine to cause diarrhea, such as the heat stable (ST) and heat labile (LT) enterotoxins (Zhang et al 2022).

This protocol shall be applied to pure ETEC pure cultures, isolated from any source, with any method, and is based on conventional PCR. The present document describes two multiplex PCRs to detect ST and LT-coding genes (ST_{human}, ST_{porcine} and LT) and five different colonization factors, mainly associated with the animal host, particularly swine.

3. Normative references

- ISO 6887 (all parts), Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination
- ISO 7218, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — General requirements and guidance for microbiological examinations.
- ISO 11133, Microbiology of food, animal feed and water — Preparation, production, storage and performance testing of culture media
- ISO 22174, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — General requirements and definitions

- ISO 22118, Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection and quantification of food-borne pathogens — Performance characteristics
- ISO 23418, Whole genome sequencing for typing and genomic characterization of foodborne bacteria — General requirements and guidance

4. Abbreviations

PCR: polymerase chain reaction

TSA: Tryptone Soy Agar

ETEC: Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli*

est_h: gene encoding the heat stable enterotoxin A (human variant)

est_p: gene encoding the heat stable enterotoxin A (porcine variant)

est_b: gene encoding the heat stable enterotoxin B

5. Procedure for the PCR determination of ETEC toxins and colonization factors coding genes

5.1 Template preparation

DNA can be purified from single colonies streaked onto solid agar plates, with any method in use in the laboratory (e.g. chelex-based non-immobilized resins). A DNA simple extraction method by boiling method is described below.

- ✓ Streak the pure STEC culture onto solid medium (e.g. TSA)
- ✓ Pick a single bacterial colony with a sterile 1 µl loop
- ✓ Suspend the colony in 100 µl of nuclease-free water and boil for 10 minutes.
- ✓ *Optional*: centrifuge at 13000rpm for 5min and retain the supernatant for use as template DNA
- ✓ Use 3-5 µl as template in PCR reactions

Important: Too much DNA (colony mass) will give non-specific bands.

5.2 Reaction mix

Set up a reaction mix according to the manufacturers recommendations of the polymerase used:

Reagent	Final Concentration
Reaction Buffer	1X
MgCl ₂	1.5 mM
dNTPs	0.2 mM
Primers	0.4 µM (each primer)
Taq polymerase	2.5 U

A ready-to-use master mix, containing the reaction buffer, MgCl₂, dNTPs and Taq Polymerase, can also be used, depending on its availability. Prepare a 25 µl mix per reaction by adding nuclease-free water and 5 µl of DNA template. A negative control shall be used in all reactions, consisting of a reaction mixture added with 5 µl of nuclease-free water. Positive controls consisting of DNA prepared from reference strains shall be added at each working session (see the reference strains' section)

5.3 Primer pairs and thermal profiles

The primer sequences and the amplicon sizes expected for the target genes detection are reported in the table below. The simultaneous detection of *est_h*, *est_p* and *lt* genes can be done, but it is not possible to distinguish among *st_h* and *st_p* given the overlapping amplicons' sizes. The amplification of the colonization factors' genes can also be carried out in a multiplex PCR, and particularly K88 and 987P can be amplified together as well as and the combination of K99, F18 and F41.

The PCRs shall be set up separately for the two targets consisting in the toxins and the colonization factors, since the annealing temperatures are not overlapping

Target	Sequence (5'-3')	Amplicon size	Thermal profile	Reference
<i>est_h</i>	TTTCGCTCAGGATGCTAA ACCAG	151 bp	94°C 2 min – 35X: 94°C 50sec, 62°C 40 sec, 72°C 50 sec – 72°C 3 min – 4°C ∞	Persson et al, 2007
	CAGGATTACAACACAATTC ACAGCAGTA			

<i>est_p</i>	CTTCCCCTCTTTTAGTCA GTCAA CTG	160 bp	“	Persson et al, 2007
	ACAGAATCGTCAGCATCA GC			
<i>eltI</i>	AAACCGGCTTTGTCAGAT ATGATGA	479 bp	“	Persson et al, 2007
	TGTGCTCAGATTCTGGGT CTCCT			
<i>fanA</i> (K99)	AATACTTGTTCAAGGAGA AA	230 bp	94°C 5 min – 30X: 94°C sec, 55 °C 30 sec min, 72°C 1 min – 72°C 5 min	Casey and Bosworth, 2009
	AACTTTGTGGTTAACTTCC T			
<i>fedA</i> (F18)	TGGTAACGTATCAGCAAC TA	313 bp	“	Casey and Bosworth, 2009
	ACTTACAGTGCTATTCGAC G			
<i>fasA</i> (987P)	AAGTTACTGCCAGTCTAT GC	409 bp	“	Casey and Bosworth, 2009
	GTA ACTCCACCGTTTGTAT C			
<i>faeG</i> (K88)	GTTGGTACAGGTCTTAAT GG	499 bp	“	Casey and Bosworth, 2009
	GAATCTGTCCGAGAATAT CA			
<i>fedA</i> subunit (F41)	AGTATCTGGTTCAGTGAT GG	612 bp	“	Casey and Bosworth, 2009
	CCACTATAAGAGGTTGAA GC			

Table 1. Primers and sequences used for target genes detection

5.4 Agarose gel electrophoresis

Prepare a 2 % (w/v) agarose gel in 1X Tris/Borate/EDTA (TBE) or Tris/Acetate/EDTA (TAE). Each well of the gel is loaded with 15 µl of each reaction added with loading dye at 1X final concentration. Run the samples in 1X running buffer (TBE or TAE) in constant voltage (100 V). Use a proper stain for visualizing on a UV transilluminator the DNA fragments in the gel after the run. A molecular weight marker suitable for assignment of the correct molecular weights to the amplicons produced (refer to table 1) shall be loaded.

5.5 Interpretation of the results

The correct band assignment is a crucial point in the assessment of the presence of the virulence genes. Samples showing amplification fragments of the expected size (See 5.4 and Annex 1) are considered as positive for related target genes. Make sure that the bands produced by the control strains match exactly the expected molecular weight, and that the negative controls are not showing any amplification products.

5.6 Reference strains

DNA template extracted from strains possessing the target genes shall be included in each analytical session as positive controls.

Examples of reference strains available for this purpose are reported below:

H10407: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *eltI*⁺, *est_p*⁺, commercially available

EF451: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *eltI*⁺, *est_p*⁺

EA22: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *est_n*⁺

Y5053 and Y5316: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *fedA*⁺ (F18)

HM1355: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *fasA*⁺ (987P)

EcA: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *faeG*⁺ (K88)

Y5209: Enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, *fedA* subunit (F41)

Reference strains to be used as positive controls can be requested at the Department of Bacteriology, Animal and Plant Health Agency, Addlestone, Surrey, UK (miranda.kirchner@apha.gov.uk), EURL for *E. coli* (<https://www.iss.it/en/web/iss-en/coli-activities-and-services>) or at the International *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella* Centre, Department of Bacteria, Parasites and Fungi, at the Statens Serum Institut (fsc@ssi.dk).

5.7 Equipment needed

- Laminar flow hood
- Laminar flow hood for PCR
- Disposable bacteriology loops of 1 and 10 µl
- 15 ml snap cap tubes
- 500 ml flasks
- 500 ml and 1l cylinders
- Bacteriology plates
- Incubator (37 ± 1 ° C)
- Fridge-freezer
- Technical scale suitable for weighing in the 0.5-100 g range
- Automatic variable volume pipettes (P10, P20, P100, P200, P1000)
- Sterile tips with anti-aerosol filter
- 1.5 ml Eppendorf type tubes
- 0.2 ml PCR tubes or 96-well PCR plates with seals
- Heating plate or Thermoblock
- Rotating agitator
- Magnetic stir bar
- Thermal cycler (no particular specific requests are required)
- Horizontal electrophoresis apparatus
- U.V. transilluminator

5.8 Reagents

- Sterile deionized water free of contaminating nucleases
- Deoxyribonucleotides in 10 mM stock solution
- Synthetic oligonucleotides in solution (100 pmoles/µl in water)
- *Taq* DNA polymerase + reaction buffer
- Tris Acetate EDTA Buffer or Tris Borate EDTA buffer
- Loading buffer (purchased ready for use)
- Agarose gel (for molecular biology)
- Agarose gel stain (purchased ready for use)
- Nutrient agar (e.g. TSA)

Acknowledgments

OH-Harmony-Cap project would like to acknowledge the following laboratories for their support and willingness to participate in the project, and allowing the proposal of the present procedure:

- The International Collaborating Centre for Reference and Research on *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella*, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark
- Department of Bacteriology, Animal and Plant Health Agency, Addlestone, Surrey, UK

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- Zhang Y, Tan P, Zhao Y and Ma X. 2022. Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli*: intestinal pathogenesis mechanisms and colonization resistance by gut microbiota, *Gut Microbes*, 14:1, 2055943

Annex 9 Decision tree for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium*

OH-Harmony-Cap: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR determinants

* It is possible to go back and do molecular typing

** Many methods available. Usually involves a mechanical disruption of oocysts before DNA extraction.

*** Several different markers used. Commonly 18S for detection of any *Cryptosporidium* spp.

Annex 10 Methods for the characterization of the different species of *Cryptosporidium*

OH-Harmony-Cap: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR determinants

References for *Cryptosporidium* detection

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Wang Y, Zhang B, Li J, Yu S, Zhang N, Liu S, Zhang Y, Li J, Ma N, Cai Y, Zhao Q. Development of a quantitative real-time PCR assay for detection of *Cryptosporidium* spp. infection and threatening caused by *Cryptosporidium parvum* subtype IIdA19G1 in diarrhea calves from Northeastern China. *Vector Borne Zoonotic Dis.* 2021 Mar;21(3):179-190. doi: 10.1089/vbz.2020.2674. Epub 2020 Dec 1. PMID: 33259769

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Mead, Jan R, and Michael J. Arrowood. *Cryptosporidium: methods and protocols.* Springer New York, 2020. Print.

References for GP60 subtyping

C. parvum, *C. hominis*, *C. cuniculus*, *C. sciurinum*, *C. tyzzeri* etc.:

Alves, M.; Xiao, L.; Sulaiman, I.; Lal, A.A.; Matos, O.; Antunes, F. Subgenotype analysis of *Cryptosporidium* isolates from humans, cattle, and zoo ruminants in Portugal. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 2003, 41, 2744–2747.

C. bovis:

Wang, W.; Wan, M.; Yang, F.; Li, N.; Xiao, L.; Feng, Y.; Guo, Y. Development and application of a *gp60*-based subtyping tool for *Cryptosporidium bovis*. *Microorganisms* 2021, 9, 2067. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9102067>

C. canis:

Jiang et al. Development of a subtyping tool for zoonotic pathogen *Cryptosporidium canis*. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 2021, 59, 3, e02474-20 DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.02474-20>

C. chipmunk genotype I:

Guo, Y., Cebelinski, E., Matusevich, C., Alderisio, K.A., Lebbad, M., McEvoy, J., Roellig, D.M., Yang, C., Feng, Y., Xiao, L., 2015. Subtyping novel zoonotic pathogen *Cryptosporidium chipmunk* genotype I. J. Clin. Microbiol. 53, 1648–1654.

For additional seq primer for *C. chipmunk* genotype (to those by Guo et al): Bujila, I., Troell, K., Fischerström, K., (...), Lebbad, M., Beser, J., 2021. *Cryptosporidium chipmunk* genotype I – An emerging cause of human cryptosporidiosis in Sweden. Infection, Genetics and Evolution. 92, 104895.

C. felis:

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Annex 10 Nomenclature of ETEC toxins (ST and LT)

Toxin subtype	Gene	Previous synonym for toxin gene	for GenBank Accession No.	Suggested synonym for toxin gene
Sta				
STp:	<i>est</i>	<i>estla</i>	AP010910	<i>estap</i>
		<i>est</i>	AP014654	
		<i>sta3</i>	M18346	
		<i>sta4</i>	JO3311	
STh:	<i>est</i>	<i>st</i>	M29255	<i>estah</i>
		<i>sta2</i>	FM649418	
STb				
STb:	<i>est</i>	<i>stb</i>	AY028790	<i>estb</i>
LT				
LT-I:	Subunit A and Subunit B of LT	<i>eltA</i>	FN649417	<i>eltIA</i>
		<i>eltB</i>	FN649417	<i>eltIB</i>
		<i>eltIp</i>		<i>eltIAB</i> *
		<i>eltIh</i>		
LT-II:	<i>eltII</i>	<i>eltIIa</i> and <i>eltIIb</i>		<i>eltIIAB</i> *
				<i>eltIIa</i>
				<i>eltIIb</i>
				<i>eltIIc</i>
				<i>eltIId</i>
				<i>eltIIe</i>

* represents the holotoxin sequence of both the A and B subunit including spacer sequences when relevant. ST = Heat stable toxin. LT = Heat Labile toxin. STp = porcine variant. STh = human variant